

Justice is Ready for Consciousness. Lawyers with Vertical Lives. Are We Really Ready?-

Personal Physical Mental and Spiritual Coherent Experience

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Abstract

Modern specialists discuss and promote the interconnection and innovation in the digitalization of justice. The digitalization of justice has been an ongoing process for many years. Digital technologies will continue to advance with great speed and acceleration, as we have already seen. "Robot Justice", "smart, online court systems", "under the 14th five-year plan, Chinese courts will upgrade to the fourth generation of smart court by 2025"- "recent technological advances in artificial intelligence (AI)", "internet of things (IOT)", "big data, block chain, data analytics" etc - how many times have we heard these words last years. Emerging technologies are reshaping the face of justice and legal work. At the same time, we have to understand what's the right thing to do?. "...I don't know whether we're ready yet to really see things the way they are. For instance, it would be a disaster if we had to get vaccinated every year,"- Federico Faggin says. Could we see the way of justice? In this paper we speak and promote for the discussion: justice as interconnection and innovation, seeing justice as consciousness and consciousness as quantum field. Drawing on personal academic experience and legal practice we conclude that not only digital technologies, not only microelectronics, but the use of quantum mechanics to know ourselves and come into contact with our deepest self, a personal physical mental and spiritual coherent experience: what is at the bottom of justice-reality. If you are intrigued on the mathematical theory based on consciousness being primary aspect of nature, we are for you here.

Keywords: Faggin, robot justice, digital technologies, lawyer/judge, consciousness, justice, Diaphany consciousness, quantum field, science of qualia, science of consciousness, dharma, legal consciousness

"As I see it,
things will not be exactly
the way they were before,
even though
our human tendency is
to go back and
do the same things
we've always done." -
Federico Faggin¹

Introduction. Let us begin by defining the terms.

"Justice is fairness in the way that people are treated,"²- English Dictionary says us.

¹ Federico Faggin (1941) is an Italian-American physicist, engineer, inventor and entrepreneur. He is best known for designing the first commercial microprocessor, the Intel 4004.

² <https://www.collinsdictionary.com/dictionary/english/achieve-justice>

'Justice' has always been a sacred word for humankind. Within the Platonism, it has been argued that Justice is a virtue³. Many centuries later, John Rawls⁴ looked at justice as 'the first virtue of social institutions'.⁵

"Justice as Fairness: Political not Metaphysical"⁶ is his essay, published in 1985. In it he comprises two main principles of liberty and equality; the second is subdivided into Fair Equality of Opportunity and the Difference Principle.

Rawls originally presented the theory in his 1971 book *A Theory of Justice*, subsequently expanding upon several of its themes in his later book titled *Political Liberalism*.

Sandel⁷ explains theories of justice, the ideas of Aristotle, Jeremy Bentham, Immanuel Kant, John Stuart Mill, Robert Nozick and John Rawls⁸. "To argue about justice is unavoidably to argue about virtues, about substantive moral and even spiritual questions", - Michael Sandel tells us in his famous lecture. He continues: "I find this in all these places I've been travelling - from India to China, to Japan and Europe and to Brazil - there is a frustration with the terms of public discourse, with a kind of absence of discussion of questions of justice and ethics and of values".⁹ "Justice' confronts us with the concepts that lurk, so often unacknowledged, beneath our conflicts,¹⁰" - Jonathan Rauch wrote in the *New York Times*.

Spirituality. We share the idea of Thomas Merton¹¹ that spiritual life is not intellectual life. It is not just thought. And of course it is not even a life of sensation, a life of feeling and experiencing the things of the spirit and the things of God. But the spiritual life does not exclude thought and feeling. It needs both. It is not a life from which mind, imagination and body are excluded. If it would be so, only few people could experience it. And again, if such would be the spiritual life, it would not be a life at all. If a man is alive, his body, soul, mind, heart and spirit should be alive. Everything must be elevated and transformed by the action of spirit.¹²

Spirituality is not a religion. There are some pretty clear ways in which religion and spirituality differ.¹³ There are wider concerns about the idea of introducing practices, traditionally seen as having a strong religious association, into a secular setting. Norman

3 Plato, *Republic*, translated and with intro by R.E. Allen, New Haven: Yale University Press, 24 (2006)

4 John Bordley Rawls (1921 – 2002) was an American moral and political philosopher in the liberal tradition. Rawls received both the Schock Prize for Logic and Philosophy and the National Humanities Medal in 1999. Rawls has often been described as one of the most influential political philosophers of the 20th century.

5 Rawls, John, *A Theory of Justice*, Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 3 (1971). Rawls was best known for this work (1971), a book that transformed how political philosophy was done for a generation. His philosophical vision of a just society, which embodied the postwar liberal dream of a more perfect America, became the basis for a philosophy known as "liberal egalitarianism." (see on liberal egalitarianism in detail: Tungodden Bertil and Cappelen Alexander, *A Liberal Egalitarian Paradox*, in *Economics and Philosophy* vol. 22 no. 3, 393-408 (2006))

6 John Rawls, *Justice as Fairness: Political not Metaphysical*, *Philosophy and Public Affairs* 14 (Summer 1985).

7 Michael Joseph Sandel (1953) is an American political philosopher and the Anne T. and Robert M. Bass Professor of Government Theory at Harvard University Law School, where his course *Justice* was the university's first course to be made freely available online and on television. He is also known for his critique of John Rawls' *A Theory of Justice* in his first book, *Liberalism and the Limits of Justice* (1982). He was elected a Fellow of the American Academy of Arts and Sciences in 2002.

8 See in detail: *Justice*, one of the most popular courses taught at Harvard College: <https://justiceharvard.org/justice/>, and <https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/justice/>

9 <https://justiceharvard.org/>

10 <https://scholar.harvard.edu/sandel/publications/justice-whats-right-thing-do>

11 Thomas Merton (1915 -1968) was an American Trappist monk, writer, theologian, mystic, poet, social activist, and scholar of comparative religion. On May 26, 1949, he was ordained to the priesthood and given the name *Father Louis*. He was a member of the Abbey of Our Lady of Gethsemani, near Bardstown, Kentucky, living there from 1941 to his death.

12 More details Thomas Merton. *Thoughts in solitude*, <https://www.monasterovirtuale.it/pensieri-nella-solitudine.html>

13 <https://au.reachout.com/articles/what-is-spirituality#:~:text=There%20are%20some%20pretty%20clear,sense%20of%20peace%20and%20purpose.>

Fisher¹⁴ says: “These teachings are those of humanity, even though they may have originated 2,600 years ago. They can be taught in secular settings.”¹⁵ Daniel J Siegel¹⁶ says: “Oftentimes, people hear the word ‘mindfulness’ and think ‘religion’, but the reality is that focusing our attention in this way is a biological process that promotes health – as a form of brain hygiene – not a religion. Various religions may encourage this health-promoting practice, but learning the skill of mindful awareness is simply a way of cultivating what we have defined as the integration of consciousness.”

Federico Faggin writes: “Spirituality is the spontaneous urge each of us feels deep within to experience and explore our personal connection with a transcendent dimension of being that goes beyond the day to day necessities. Its origin is an innate sense that we are all connected somehow and that our life and experience has meaning and purpose.

Spirituality relies on first-person experience of the transcendent, rather than belief in a particular doctrine. It is experiential, open, and directed toward finding our own inner truth about the nature of union.”¹⁷

Spirituality depends on personal practice.¹⁸

Consciousness. Consciousness has become a common expression in daily conversations, but it expresses a number of different concepts depending on the meaning of the speaker and is related to other phrases or terms that have slightly different connotations: 4,¹⁹ 5,²⁰ 7²¹ stages of consciousness, levels of consciousness,²² The Barrett Model,²³ level of consciousness (LOC),²⁴ the Consciousness-Intelligence-Knowledge Pyramid: An 8x8 Layer Model,²⁵ heightened consciousness,²⁶ raising consciousness,²⁷ legal/justice consciousness etc. Freud divided human consciousness into three levels of awareness:

14 Zoketsu Norman Fischer is an American poet, writer, and Soto Zen priest, teaching and practicing in the lineage of Shunryu Suzuki (Shunryu Suzuki, often called Suzuki Roshi. May, 1904 – 1971) was a Sōtō Zen monk and teacher who is renowned for founding the first Zen Buddhist monastery outside Asia (Tassajara Zen Mountain Center). Suzuki founded San Francisco Zen Center which, along with its affiliate temples, comprises one of the most influential Zen organizations in the United States. A book of his teachings, *Zen Mind, Beginner's Mind*, is one of the most popular books on Zen and Buddhism in the West). He is a Dharma heir of Sojun Mel Weitsman, from whom he received Dharma transmission in 1988. Fischer served as co-abbot of the San Francisco Zen Center from 1995–2000, after which he founded the Everyday Zen Foundation in 2000, a network of Buddhist practice group and related projects in Canada, the United States and Mexico (<http://everydayzen.org/about-everyday-zen/teachers/>). Fischer has published more than twenty-five books of poetry and non-fiction, as well as numerous poems, essays and articles in Buddhist magazines and poetry journals (<https://www.normanfischer.org/biography/>).

15 https://www.garrisoninstitute.org/images/Its_all_in_the_mind.pdf

16 Daniel J. Siegel (born July 17, 1957) is a clinical professor of psychiatry at the UCLA School of Medicine and executive director of the Mindful Awareness Research Centre.

17 <https://wsimag.com/science-and-technology/64792-the-union-of-science-and-spirituality>

18 See interview with Santikaro (Robert Larson), who had trained under the famous Thai Buddhist teacher, Buddhadasa Bhikku. According to him, in the west, there are three forms that mindfulness has been shaped into:

[https://www.huffpost.com/entry/is-there-anything-spiritu_b_8021384?](https://www.huffpost.com/entry/is-there-anything-spiritu_b_8021384?guccounter=1&guce_referrer=aHR0cHM6Ly93d3cuZ29vZ2xlLmNvbS8&guce_referrer_sig=AQAAACyXEo42DAtwGm2DqjM0ujjORIHn5Qx-iTmzhDGIHx2JCCqKzs5gBcS0irWpIBxDnpzfrE167YQYyGHJOGg_PgaesyBq-XniWAsmuLMb-S5YvN-CbdWKTvx9qjQPfs1ZZMU4D-NqM6vuoVM9IBLWTRfbOJFmXODfu2FJ-HbuZ4Ym)

[guccounter=1&guce_referrer=aHR0cHM6Ly93d3cuZ29vZ2xlLmNvbS8&guce_referrer_sig=AQAAACyXEo42DAtwGm2DqjM0ujjORIHn5Qx-iTmzhDGIHx2JCCqKzs5gBcS0irWpIBxDnpzfrE167YQYyGHJOGg_PgaesyBq-XniWAsmuLMb-S5YvN-CbdWKTvx9qjQPfs1ZZMU4D-NqM6vuoVM9IBLWTRfbOJFmXODfu2FJ-HbuZ4Ym](https://www.huffpost.com/entry/is-there-anything-spiritu_b_8021384?guccounter=1&guce_referrer=aHR0cHM6Ly93d3cuZ29vZ2xlLmNvbS8&guce_referrer_sig=AQAAACyXEo42DAtwGm2DqjM0ujjORIHn5Qx-iTmzhDGIHx2JCCqKzs5gBcS0irWpIBxDnpzfrE167YQYyGHJOGg_PgaesyBq-XniWAsmuLMb-S5YvN-CbdWKTvx9qjQPfs1ZZMU4D-NqM6vuoVM9IBLWTRfbOJFmXODfu2FJ-HbuZ4Ym)

19 <https://www.forbes.com/sites/jimblasingame/2014/07/07/the-four-levels-of-performance-consciousness/?sh=3e0ed1c02b46>

20 <https://www.cleverism.com/5-stages-of-consciousness-evolution/>

21 <https://tmhome.com/books-videos/7-states-of-consciousness-video-interview/>

22 <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S136466131630002X>

23 <https://www.barrettacademy.com/7-levels-of-consciousness>

24 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Altered_level_of_consciousness

25 <https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/8344/bd8f796dca23a4ed2f352c82818af50d65fb.pdf>

26 <https://www.forbes.com/sites/forbescoachescouncil/2020/07/27/raising-your-consciousness-requires-more-than-hot-air/?sh=40865e593e45>

27 <https://methods.sagepub.com/reference/encyc-of-case-study-research/n81.xml>

the conscious, preconscious, and unconscious. Each of these levels corresponds and overlaps with Freud's ideas of the id, ego, and superego.²⁸

There are the different meanings of the term consciousness and similar phrases in regard to personal development.

"I regard consciousness as fundamental. I regard matter as derivative from consciousness. We cannot get behind consciousness. Everything that we talk about, everything that we regard as existing, postulates consciousness", -²⁹Max Planck³⁰ said. Austrian physicist Erwin Schrödinger³¹ is known for the phrase "The total number of minds in the universe is one. In fact, consciousness is a singularity phasing within all beings"³² which best summarizes his philosophical outlook on the nature of reality. The phrase implies that the apparent multiplicity of minds is just an illusion and that there is only one mind, or one consciousness, that expresses itself in a myriad of ways. In such a world view, a separation between subject and object does not exist, there is no existence of a subject on the one side and perception of an object on the other. In a world without the subject-object split, we are all an expression of the one.

Schrödinger also stated that "Consciousness cannot be accounted for in physical terms. For consciousness is absolutely fundamental. It cannot be accounted for in terms of anything else."³³ This reflects the idea of panpsychism³⁴, the view that all existence is permeated by consciousness and that consciousness is the underlying reality – rather than just something that is produced by brains of a certain complexity.

In contemporary times, science has pushed itself to hypothesize that human consciousness is independent of the body.³⁵ Finally, science is expanding its borders beyond the limits of the body, to begin to explore, in the context of quantum physics, the reality of human consciousness subsisting beyond the physical body. The existence of the biofield³⁶ challenges reductionist approaches. Of course, the existence of biofield presents its own challenges regarding how it may inform an integrated understanding of thought, conscience (consciousness) and the living universe.

28 <https://courses.lumenlearning.com/boundless-psychology/chapter/introduction-to-consciousness/>

29 <https://physicstoday.scitation.org/doi/full/10.1063/PT.3.3343>

30 Max Karl Ernst Ludwig Planck (1858 – 1947) was a German theoretical physicist whose discovery of energy quanta won him the Nobel Prize in Physics in 1918. Planck made many substantial contributions to theoretical physics, but his fame as a physicist rests primarily on his role as the originator of quantum theory, which revolutionized human understanding of atomic and subatomic processes. In 1948, the German scientific institution Kaiser Wilhelm Society (of which Planck was twice president) was renamed Max Planck Society (MPG). The MPG now includes 83 institutions representing a wide range of scientific directions.

31 Erwin Rudolf Josef Alexander Schrödinger (1887 – 1961) was a Nobel Prize-winning Austrian-Irish physicist who developed a number of fundamental results in quantum theory: the Schrödinger equation provides a way to calculate the wave function of a system and how it changes dynamically in time. In addition, he wrote many works on various aspects of physics: statistical mechanics and thermodynamics, physics of dielectrics, colour theory, electrodynamics, general relativity, and cosmology, and he made several attempts to construct a unified field theory. In his book *What Is Life?* Schrödinger addressed the problems of genetics, looking at the phenomenon of life from the point of view of physics. He paid great attention to the philosophical aspects of science, ancient, and oriental philosophical concepts, ethics, and religion. He also wrote on philosophy and theoretical biology. He is also known for his "Schrödinger's cat" thought experiment.

32 https://www.reddit.com/r/quotes/comments/hn91k8/the_total_number_of_minds_in_the_universe_is_one/

33 As quoted in *The Observer* (11 January 1931); also in *Psychic Research* (1931), Vol. 25, 91;

https://en.wikiquote.org/wiki/Erwin_Schr%C3%B6dinger

34 <https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/panpsychism/#:~:text=Panpsychism%20is%20the%20view%20that,ubiquitous%20in%20the%20natural%20world.&text=Panpsychism%2C%20strange%20as%20it%20may,a%20unified%20conception%20of%20nature.>

35 See also: <https://theconversation.com/consciousness-how-can-i-experience-things-that-arent-real-139600>

36 In sum, a biofield is an energy blueprint that corresponds holistically to an entire organism. It allows for rapid communication throughout the body. It is the matrix that connects our physical, emotional, and mental dimensions. See more here: <https://one2onephysicaltherapy.com/what-are-biofield-therapies/>

The state-of the art. Modern specialists discuss and promote the interconnection and innovation in the digitalisation of justice.³⁷ The digitalisation of justice has been an ongoing process for many years that has seen an increase in speed and width lately, triggered by technological developments, growing public sector commitment and – most recently– COVID-19. It is now that lawyers and other professionals are discussing the sustainable future of cross-border judicial communication in the EU, the use of artificial intelligence for justice applications worldwide and the capacities for video conferencing in court sessions as part of our digital sovereignty. "Robot Justice"³⁸- "smart, online court systems"³⁹- "under the 14th five-year plan, Chinese courts will upgrade to the fourth generation of smart court by 2025"⁴⁰- how many times have we heard these words last years. Digital technologies will continue to advance with great speed and acceleration, as we have already seen. China's courts use data analytics and blockchain evidence storage on the way to first AI-integrated legal system⁴¹, the Estonian Ministry of Justice has officially asked Ott Velsberg, the country's chief data officer, to design a "robot judge".⁴² Emerging technologies are reshaping the face of justice and legal work. Recent technological advances in artificial intelligence (AI), internet of things (IOT), big data, block chain, data analytics etc. have enabled global tech majors to harness the data obtained in data processing to deliver actionable business insights often converted into data products. This process known as "digital transformation" has the potential to transform the value proposition of their global clients and is rapidly moving the service providers from the back office to the front office handling product design and development. This is a sensational leap forward for the IT consulting/service providers from the cost cutting of the outsourcing era and raises critical legal issues addressed for the lawyers. As technology continues to change the way in which we work and function, there are predictions that many aspects of human activity will be replaced or supported by newer technologies.⁴³ According to physicians, within fifty years, computers will be able to become perfectly conscious and will replace men and women in accomplishing almost every task.⁴⁴

At the same time, we have to understand what's the right thing to do?

"..I don't know whether we're ready yet to really see things the way they are. For instance, it would be a disaster if we had to get vaccinated every year,"⁴⁵- Federico Faggin says. And we're fully agreed. Could we see the way of justice? Yes, we could, it would be that one, based on the Science of consciousness⁴⁶, seeing as the primary aspect of nature.

Not only newer technologies, not only microelectronics, but the use of quantum mechanics to know ourselves and come into contact with our deepest self: what is at the bottom of justice-reality. In this paper we speak and promote for the discussion of justice as interconnection and innovation, seeing the innovation in the pattern: justice as consciousness and consciousness as quantum field.

37 <https://fra.europa.eu/en/news/2020/interconnection-and-innovation-digitalisation-justice> ; <https://www.eu2020.de/eu2020-en/events/-/2421866> ; <https://eu2020-bmjv-ejustice.de/en> ; https://www.bmjv.de/EN/EU/EU_2020_en/Presse/120820_conference_digitalisation.html etc

38 <https://www.lexisnexis.ca/en-ca/ihc/2020-02/robot-justice-chinas-use-of-internet-courts.page>

39 <https://www.lawgazette.co.uk/news/lawyers-will-be-more-in-demand-than-ever-with-online-courts-says-yos/5110434.article>

40 <https://www.scmp.com/news/china/politics/article/3124815/chinas-courts-use-data-analytics-and-blockchain-evidence>

41 <https://conflictoflaws.net/2021/how-emerging-technologies-shape-the-face-of-chinese-courts%EF%BC%9F/comment-page-1/>

42 <https://futurism.com/the-byte/estonia-robot-judge>

43 <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC7605294/>

44 <https://venice.sciencegallery.com/blog/federico-faggin-on-the-nature-of-consciousness>

45 <https://www.domusweb.it/en/news/2021/05/21/federico-faggin-were-people-machines-will-not-replace-us.html>

46 <https://cristinagabetti.com/en/federico-faggin-the-science-of-consciousness/>

“The matter is the ink with which consciousness writes its own self-knowing”⁴⁷.

Among the most prestigious names, we refer to that of Federico Faggin, father of the microchip and touchscreen, who, in his speeches and papers, focuses on consciousness and awareness, the fundamental elements if we look to the future. “We are at the threshold of the age of conscience” – explains Faggin. “The machines are not better than us, we stop projecting on the machine properties that it does not have. Instead we develop our conscience, so as not to become slaves of those who produce machines”.⁴⁸

Federico Faggin, the physician who invented the first microprocessor, the man to whom we owe technology the way we know it today, one of the pioneers of the Silicon Valley, within his career was moved by the ambition of creating a conscious computer. What he found out is simply that it could not exist. The Italian inventor’s research led him to even more revolutionary discoveries than the technology behind the 4004, but with only one conclusion: a robot will never be conscious, cannot have a piece of DNA.⁴⁹

Faggin accepts the secret of the reality: he takes us by the hand and brings us outside, to look up, to feel the cosmos pulsing around us; he calls us to open the windows of the house to let in the great winds of history, to feel a living part of an immense life. Somebody suffers, somebody is born here, in an immense life. The reality often writhes like a woman with child about to give birth⁵⁰, - says Isaiah, - but to produce life: it is in continuous gestation, it carries another reality in the womb.

We are with child; we writhe in pain; we give birth to wind.

The earth resounds with an infinite cry, but Faggin asks us not to lose our hearts, not to walk with our heads down, with downcast eyes. He asks us: look up and lift up your heads, science is ready for consciousness.⁵¹ “Look up and lift up your heads, because your redemption draws near,” - Luke describes *quasi* the same words of Jesus.⁵²

In today’s world, the relationship between law and spirituality ranges from hostility to peaceful coexistence through mindfulness.⁵³ Law and spirituality are like two separate silos that do not communicate with each other—a duality that is impossible to resolve without a new worldview that contains the two, that unites them both. We believe it is possible, but only through the active personal effort of each lawyer/judge at the physical, emotional, and spiritual levels of existence. It requires the deliberate choice of that union of each human soul. It is not something that can be found in codes or case-law. Only by walking one’s path with total commitment can union be gradually achieved. As union is progressively achieved, creativity, motive energy, and proper action will be mobilized to collectively solve the many challenges now facing humanity—for the benefit of all life.

Einstein is widely quoted as saying: “The intuitive mind is a sacred gift and the rational mind is a faithful servant. We have created a society that honors the servant and has forgotten the gift.”⁵⁴

Intuition is a powerful human possibility that rests on the ability to grasp the hidden in things and which makes use of a good dose of imagination, the ability to “see far” with the

47 Federico Faggin, quoted in <https://galileocommission.org/science-is-ready-for-consciousness-federico-faggin/>

48 <https://www.wired.it/attualita/tech/2019/05/25/faggin-wired-next-fest-2019/> ;

<https://magazine.impactscool.com/en/i-nostri-eventi/workshop-talk-ed-eventi-il-wired-next-fest-di-impactscool/>

49 <https://venice.sciencegallery.com/blog/federico-faggin-on-the-nature-of-consciousness>

50 <https://biblehub.com/isaiah/26-18.htm>

51 https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=14Q_W6H_nZk

52 <https://biblehub.com/luke/21-28.htm>

53 See inter alia, Olga Nickole Kuyan. (2021). To Take Law Seriously. Via quantum physics, mechanics. We Vote for Mindful Lawyers/Judges, becoming Political Actors. For Development, Unity of Diversity, Inclusion, Sustainability. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5731565> ; Olga Nickole Kuyan. (2021). Mindfulness, Quantum Physics and "well-being is a two-way street". <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5732075> ; Olga Nickole Kuyan. (2021). Finding Ways to Be Lawyers in Today's World, Calling to Have the Courage to Make Changes. Mindfulness Matters: Thought, Attention, Awakening. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5734445>

54 <https://www.cnbc.com/2017/06/29/steve-jobs-and-albert-einstein-both-attributed-their-extraordinary-success-to-this-personality-trait.html>

inner eyes, which Einstein exalted and which made him "see" things which were discovered after a long time.

Intuition is a non-visual seeing, a flash, "the whisper of the Soul"⁵⁵- says Krishnamurti⁵⁶ -, a particular way of "grasping", therefore a whisper of that ability to penetrate beyond the veil that envelops reality, into the vast territory of the beyond.

We, placed in the rich flow of life, surrounded by a reality full of messages, try to find the beyond that we perceive. Only if we get out of the noise of the world, life speaks to us silently and we perceive the thoughtfulness of life. Solitudes speak to us, immensity has its own special language, searching tells us that there is always something behind the horizon. And we can go beyond, we have a great and extraordinary possibility, a fruitful uterus, the last journey before landing.

This is the great gift of life. The other, reason, fruit of the mind, is its movement, it is reflecting on things, it has the function of the servant, of one who recognizes the greatness of the first and honors it.

Until recently it was not possible to speak on "imagination" and "intuition" in science. In fact, the scientific method is based on the demonstration, the experiment. Now we consider our ability - intuition / imagination - which comes before reason / logic, moreover. It is considered in the sense that it takes intuition and imagination to formulate the theories, which must then be demonstrated. The new science helps us in this, as it rests on something that is similar to intuition or rather uses it.

"There need no longer be a duality between mind and matter,"- Faggin says. "With consciousness you can reach reality from the inside." He makes a startling suggestion - that matter is the ink with which consciousness writes its own self-knowing.⁵⁷

What modern people, lawyers and scientists tend to forget is that technologies would not exist if humans had not created them. People grew with the conviction that they were made only by flash and bones and that perception was mainly a reaction to external stimuli.

Duality between mind and matter. Pierre Teilhard de Chardin⁵⁸ wrote on the reality of spirit-matter, inevitably translated into and confirmed by a structure of the spirit.⁵⁹ It is worth quoting a passage from Chardin's Evolution of Chastity⁶⁰: it is in these invisible and, we might almost say, immaterial zones that we can look for true initiation into unity. The depths we attribute to matter are no more than the reflection of the peaks of spirit.⁶¹ "When our determination changes", - Daisaku Ikeda⁶² writes- "everything will begin to move in the

55 <https://quotefancy.com/quote/986613/Jiddu-Krishnamurti-Intuition-is-the-whisper-of-the-soul>

56 Jiddu Krishnamurti (1895 – 1986) was a philosopher, speaker and writer. His interests included psychological revolution, the nature of mind, meditation, inquiry, human relationships, and bringing about radical change in society. He stressed the need for a revolution in the psyche of every human being and emphasised that such revolution cannot be brought about by any external entity, be it religious, political, or social.

57 https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=14Q_W6H_nZk

58 Pierre Teilhard de Chardin, S.J. (1881 – 1955), was a French Jesuit priest and scientist, professor of geology at the Catholic Institute in Paris, director of the National Geologic Survey of China, and director of the National Research Center of France. He charted a new path in reconciling Christian theology with evolutionary science. Teilhard de Chardin was a prophet, a great intuitive, a mind open to the spirit (*grace*, say the clergymen), an excellent intelligence who knew how to look from above and had a multimedia vision of things which is the evolutionary vision.

59 Teilhard de Chardin Pierre, Sketch of a Personalistic Universe (1936). Hymn of the Universe (1961) is perhaps the work of Pierre Teilhard's that stands alone in that it contains almost no scientific treatises. It is mainly a poetic/spiritual testament to the world of spirit in matter. It envisions Christ as the heart of the universe, in the heart of matter.

60 See <https://teilhard.com/tag/the-evolution-of-chastity/>

61 Teilhard de Chardin Pierre, The Evolution of Chastity (1934), as translated by René Hague in Toward the Future (1975)

62 Daisaku Ikeda (1928) is a Japanese philosopher, educator, Buddhist teacher and activist, third president of the national section of the Soka Gakkai in the period 1960 - 1979, is currently the president Ikeda, is defined as one of the most important Buddhist spiritual leaders of the second half of the 20th century and the 2000s, along with the Dalai Lama and Thích Nhất Hạnh.

direction we want". The moment we decide to be victorious, every nerve and fiber in our being will immediately head towards our success. If, on the other hand, we think that we *will never make it* then in that instant, each of our cells will be emptied and will succumb. Justice, wellbeing, happiness, peace, consciousness, religion, everything are both the physical and spiritual aspects.

Professor Tiller⁶³'s research is summarized by himself with a thought of the Buddha: "All that we are is the result of what we have thought. The mind is everything. What we think we become".⁶⁴

Physics assumes the existence of matter, energy, space, and time (MEST) with certain fundamental properties and seeks to derive all the other observable properties by using a mathematical theory founded on relationships between those properties. The validity of this approach is based on the experimentally verifiable predictions of the theory as it applies to any physical phenomenon. The existence of our conscious inner reality, however, cannot be explained with the current theories in which inert matter comes before consciousness.

Faggin offers "to postulate that consciousness is an irreducible property of MEST, like the electrical charge or the spin of elementary particles, rather than emerging somehow from complex organizations of unconscious matter,"⁶⁵ as the postulates are considered true without proof.

Tiller, conducting a rigorous experimental and theoretical study in field of psycho-energetic science,⁶⁶ has developed ideas that go far beyond conventional scientific theories on the nature of human consciousness: he hypothesizes the existence of subtle energies that go beyond the four fundamental forces,⁶⁷ which work in concert with human consciousness. Tiller views humans as spiritual beings clothed in a bio-body, also endowed with enormous powers that they are not even aware of. Tiller believes that our consciousness is generated when the spirit enters dense matter.

Judges/lawyers, any man should comprehend that the human being is not only equipped with the physical body, only, but also with other non-physical structures, composed of more subtle substances and which have their own specific function.

In the paper titled "Social Values in Europe etc" we've forwarded the idea that changing mind changes man's conscience, reflected by consciousness.⁶⁸

We've started from the Dualism,⁶⁹ introduced into the history of modern philosophy by Descartes. He held that the mind is a nonphysical substance. Descartes clearly identified the mind with consciousness and self-awareness and distinguished this from the brain as the seat of intelligence.⁷⁰

63 William A. Tiller is emeritus professor of Science and Engineering of Materials, at Stanford University. Tiller spent 34 years in academia, after having been a consultative physicist at Westinghouse Research Laboratories for nine years, he has published over 250 scientific papers.

64 <https://www.goodreads.com/quotes/1296640-all-that-we-are-is-the-result-of-what-we>

65 <http://www.fagginfoundation.org/articles/the-nature-of-consciousness/>

66 Tiller William A, Psychoenergetic Science (2007)

67 <https://www.britannica.com/science/fundamental-interaction>

68 Olga Nickole Papkova Kuyan. Social Values in Europe. Protecting Freedom of Thought, Conscience, Religion, Creating What?: Justice, Sophia, Phronesis. Authorea. July 14, 2021. DOI: 10.22541/au.162626095.53333722/v1

69 It is actually a much older concept, which appears in fact already in the works of Plato. In the philosophy of mind, mind-body dualism denotes either the view that mental phenomena are non-physical (Hart WD, Dualism, 265–67 in *A Companion to the Philosophy of Mind*, edited by S. Guttenplan. Oxford: Blackwell (1996)) or that the mind and body are distinct and separable.(Crane Tim; Patterson Sarah, Introduction. History of the Mind-Body Problem,1–2 (2001) the assumption that mind and body are distinct (essentially, dualism)) Thus, it encompasses a set of views about the relationship between mind and matter, as well as between subject and object, and is contrasted with other positions, such as physicalism and enactivism, in the mind-body problem.

70 Robinson Howard, Dualism (rev.). The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy, edited by Edward N. Zalta (2016); Descartes René. [1641], Meditations on First Philosophy, 1–62 in The Philosophical Writings of René Descartes 2, translated by J. Cottingham, R. Stoothoff, and D. Murdoch. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press (1984)

“Man is a personality not by nature but by spirit. By nature he is only an individual”⁷¹: this is the anthropology of the Russian philosopher Nikolai Berdjaev⁷². Judge/lawyer, any human being is not a simple individual; he/she is, or must strive to become, a personality. For Berdjaev, the truth is found in the personality, not in the individual: the individual is such for a purely biological and social fact; but his inner truth, his vocation, the purpose of his entire existence, emerge only when he sets out to become a personality, realizing his own ontological potential, which is extra-natural and participates in the divine.

In the paper titled “Civil Justice, Discretion, Consciousness etc”⁷³ we’ve already hypothesized that for the purpose of Justice, the new philosophy of the consciousness is necessary. We’ve debated on the meaning of the integration of human interest (of a judge/lawmaker/lawyer) and a state interest on the ground of the common aim, rooted in their uniform spiritual culture. We’ve hypothesized that (1) the main substance of politics comes to indissoluble identity of human and state interests; (2) politics is the art to unite of humans.

Nikolai Berdjaev does not believe in democracy; better: he does not believe in materialist democracy, which arises from demagogy, that is from the fondling of the lowest instincts of crowds.

The mind–body problem should bring a judge/lawyer to Plato who said in dialogue “Gorgias”: “the body is the prison of the soul.”⁷⁴ But originally the phrase is of Pythagoras. The Pythagorean philosophers believed that the body was the prison of the soul. Judges/lawyers can’t be based on materialism. They should be enlightened. The set of such structures, unrecognized by Western science based on materialism, is called Aura⁷⁵. For centuries it’s recognized by Eastern reasoning. The traditions of Eastern thought consider the spiritual world as the ultimate truth.⁷⁶

Buddhists are aware of their own existence, unlike plants and lower sentient beings who have no awareness. Their Buddhahood is dormant, latent. Buddhist knowledge awakens the enlightened being as was Buddha Sakyamuni himself.⁷⁷ Buddha means enlightened. The Sakyamuni Buddha was born about twenty five centuries ago and attained Buddhist consciousness through his own enlightenment. Therefore Buddha is an abstract noun, and also Buddha is a proper name that has a profound meaning. The Buddha consists of two elements, called mind and body⁷⁸, buddha and the place of buddha, buddha and the domain of buddha, the soul and the place of the soul, the spirit and the body of the spirit. In the West the spiritual side is called *spirit* and the material side is called body. In the East they speak of the five skandhas.⁷⁹ The material side is called rupa, while the spiritual side is divided into four elements:

71 Berdyaev N. Slavery and Freedom, 21, (1939)

72 Nikolai Alexandrovich Berdyaev (1874 – 1948) was a Russian philosopher, theologian, and Christian existentialist who emphasized the existential spiritual significance of human freedom and the human person.

73 Olga Papkova. CIVIL JUSTICE DISCRETION CONSCIOUSNESS MINDFULNESS. Authorea. February 18, 2021. DOI: 10.22541/au.161360710.05001740/v1

74 Probably it was written around 386 BC.

75 An aura or human energy field is a colored emanation said to enclose a human body or any animal or object. In some esoteric positions, the aura is described as a subtle body. See more in: Olga Nickole Papkova Kuyan. Social Values in Europe. Protecting Freedom of Thought, Conscience, Religion, Creating What?: Justice, Sophia, Phronesis. Authorea. July 14, 2021. DOI: 10.22541/au.162626095.53333722/v1

76 Venturini Riccardo L'ESPERIENZA DEL CORPO. TRA BUDDHISMO E MODERNITÀ. in M. B. Gnani Montelatici (a cura di), Il valore della pluralità delle culture – La cultura del Buddismo, Faenza, Edit. Faenza, 157-90 (2002)

77 Shakyamuni Buddha is the founder of the Buddhist religion. He lived and taught in India in the sixth century B.C.E See in detail: <https://www.khanacademy.org/humanities/art-asia/beginners-guide-asian-culture/buddhist-art-culture/a/the-buddha-shakyamuni>

78 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Buddhism_and_the_body#:~:text=The%20Buddhist%20tradition%20regards%20the,mind%20as%20being%20mutually%20dependent.&text=The%20Buddha%20taught%20that%20there,physical%2C%20emotional%20and%20cognitive%20components.

79 <https://www.lionsroar.com/what-are-the-five-skandhas/>

the first is sensory perception (vedana);
the second is thought (samjna);
the third is mental motion (samskara);
the fourth is consciousness (vijnan).

The creative power of the universe is not a human being; it's the Buddha. What sees, what hears, is not the eye or the ear, but the consciousness. It is the Buddha.

In Buddhism, every phenomenon, material or spiritual, visible or invisible, is a manifestation of the same universal Basic Law - or primary cause of life - defined Myohorenge-kyo by Nichiren Daishonin.⁸⁰ Both aspects are absolutely inseparable and of equal importance. This principle is expressed in Japanese with the term shiki shin funi. Shiki = body, matter. Shin = mind, spirit. Funi = two but not two, not two but two. Body and mind are two sides of the same coin.

Nichiren Daishonin writes to one of his followers: "A person can know the thoughts of another by listening to his voice. This happens because the physical aspect reveals the spiritual one, but these aspects, which are one in substance, manifest themselves as two distinct aspects."⁸¹

For our whole lives we have been instructed to separate science from philosophy, to oppose religion and physics, but many physicists have begun to describe the universe in words that resemble Eastern philosophy. Bohm⁸² talks about the "dimension of consciousness beyond the concrete world of our ordinary experience"⁸³. Capra⁸⁴ discusses the "web of connectedness which cannot be described in words"⁸⁵. John Wheeler⁸⁶ summarized the holographic view of the universe when he said, "There may be no such thing as the 'glittering central mechanism of the universe.'⁸⁷... Not machinery but magic may be the better description of the treasure that is waiting".⁸⁸

Leading European Universities talk on Body-Mind-Science, based on lively conversations with the Dalai Lama.⁸⁹ Rich with lucid instructions and practical insights, Mind Science dispels the metaphysical haze that all too often surrounds the subject of meditation. These

80 "This is the most important teaching. It is the teaching that earthly desires are Illumination and the sufferings of life and death are Nirvana... The sufferings become Nirvana when it is understood that the entity of human life is neither generated nor destroyed in its cycle of birth and death." (Nichiren) Nichiren (1222-1282) was a Japanese Buddhist monk, founder of Nichiren Buddhism, one of the major movements of Japanese Buddhism that includes different schools of thought, all deriving from the Buddhist branch called Mahayana. Nichiren was a prolific writer. After his death, he was bestowed the title Nichiren Dai-Bosatsu by the Emperor Go-Kōgon in 1358 and the title Risshō Daishi (Great Teacher of Correction) was conferred posthumously through imperial edict by the Emperor Taisho in 1922. The reference relies to the Lotus Sutra, preached by Buddha Shakyamuni.

81 <https://www.sgi-italia.org/unicita-di-corpo-e-mente/>

82 David Joseph Bohm (1917–1992) was an American scientist who has been described as one of the most significant theoretical physicists of the 20th century and who contributed unorthodox ideas to quantum theory, neuropsychology and the philosophy of mind.

83 <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC7513019/>

84 Fritjof Capra (born February 1, 1939) is an Austrian-born American physicist, systems theorist and deep ecologist. In 1995, he became a founding director of the Center for Ecoliteracy in Berkeley, California. He is on the faculty of Schumacher College. Capra is the author of several books, including *The Tao of Physics* (1975), *The Turning Point* (1982), *Uncommon Wisdom* (1988), *The Web of Life* (1996), and *The Hidden Connections* (2002), and co-author of *The Systems View of Life* (2014).

85 <https://www.capracourse.net/wp-content/uploads/2015/12/Introduction.pdf>

86 John Archibald Wheeler (1911 – 2008) was an American theoretical physicist. He was largely responsible for reviving interest in general relativity in the United States after World War II. Wheeler also worked with Niels Bohr in explaining the basic principles behind nuclear fission. Together with Gregory Breit, Wheeler developed the concept of the Breit–Wheeler process. He is best known for popularizing the term "black hole," as to objects with gravitational collapse already predicted during the early 20th century, for inventing the terms "quantum foam", "neutron moderator", "wormhole" and "it from bit", and for hypothesizing the "one-electron universe".

87 <https://www.jstor.org/stable/27845173>

88 <https://www.statpac.org/walonick/reality.htm>

89 For ex, see: <https://en.unistra.fr/about-us/body-mind-science-conversations-with-the-dalai-lama> ;

<https://greenreport.it/news/scienze-e-ricerca/dalai-lama-alluniversita-pisa-simposio-the-mindscience-of-reality/>

conversations show how to bring mindfulness into everyday life, while clearly explaining its many spiritual and health benefits.

Federico Faggin's nature of consciousness opens new doors for the interpretation of reality. Faggin came to the conviction that the energy that science had identified as the basis of reality⁹⁰ is nothing more than an immense original quantum field, from which everything originates.

The ideas of modern scientists, Faggin and Heisenberg⁹¹ including, are in some ways very close to the doctrines of Heraclitus⁹².

Inter alia, Werner Heisenberg, replacing the word "fire" of Heraclitus⁹³ with the word "energy" repeats his statements verbatim from modern point of view. Heisenberg writes that the energy is in fact the substance of which all elementary particles, all atoms and therefore all things are made, and energy is what moves. Energy is a substance since its total sum does not change, and since elementary particles can actually be made up of this substance as it can be seen in many experiments on the production of elementary particles. Energy can be changed into motion, heat, light and tension. Energy can be called the fundamental cause of any change in the world".⁹⁴

Energy can be called the fundamental cause of justice.

What we have learned from Faggin's and Heisenberg's ideas is that we must lay down all our preconceptions about Justice that are the result of our reforms, experience and our wishes, and instead let science, mathematics show us the way.

The Italian physician Federico Faggin proposes a theory in which everything we are supposed to consider "our world" is in fact only the reflection of our comprehension of the world captured through feelings and emotions and translated in symbols. But It would require a strong effort and a significant dose of honesty and integrity to imagine a non-mechanic reality, a world with no objects, space or time, but only created through consciousness. This idea has now become a theory, which physicists, scientists and scholars of various disciplines work on and which, according to the path of science, is waiting to be discussed. With this theory the spiritual enters the world of science. This is an enormously revolutionary step. We share his idea and we put the spiritual in the world of Law. In the paper titled "Social Values in Europe etc"⁹⁵ we've discussed the spirituality in law through energy-engaged law, sophia-energy.

Lawyers with vertical lives. Yes, till now we are tempted to look only at the immediate things, perhaps so as not to stumble into the rubble that clutters the ground, but if we do

90 <https://www.scientificamerican.com/article/is-there-a-thing-or-a-relationship-between-things-at-the-bottom-of-things/>

91 Werner Karl Heisenberg (1901 –1976) was a German theoretical physicist and one of the key pioneers of quantum mechanics. He published his work in 1925 in a breakthrough paper. In the subsequent series of papers with Max Born and Pascual Jordan, during the same year, this matrix formulation of quantum mechanics was substantially elaborated. He is known for the uncertainty principle, which he published in 1927. Heisenberg was awarded the 1932 Nobel Prize in Physics "for the creation of quantum mechanics"

92 Heraclitus of Ephesus (c. 535 – c. 475 BC, fl. 500 BC) was an Ancient Greek, pre-Socratic, Ionian philosopher. His paradoxical philosophy and appreciation for wordplay and cryptic utterances has earned him the epithet "The Obscure" since antiquity. He wrote a single work, only fragments of which have survived, increasing the obscurity associated with him. Heraclitus has thus been the subject of numerous interpretations. According to the Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy, Heraclitus has been seen as a "material monist or a process philosopher; a scientific cosmologist, a metaphysician and a religious thinker; an empiricist, a rationalist, a mystic; a conventional thinker and a revolutionary; a developer of logic—one who denied the law of non-contradiction; the first genuine philosopher and an anti-intellectual obscurantist. See also: <https://fs.blog/2013/10/heraclitus-fragments/>

93 <https://classicalwisdom.com/philosophy/pre-socratics/heraclitus-fire-flux/>

94 Heisenberg Werner, Physics and Philosophy: The Revolution in Modern Science, Harper & Row, 1962

95 Olga Nickole Papkova Kuyan. Social Values in Europe. Protecting Freedom of Thought, Conscience, Religion, Creating What?: Justice, Sophia, Phronesis. Authorea. July 14, 2021.

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not raise our heads we will never see rainbows. "You'll never find rainbows if you're looking down,⁹⁶" - Charlie Chaplin wrote.

Men and women on the way, head held high: this is how we see modern lawyers/judges. People with vertical lives.

Justice is interconnection; any case, any trial is relationship, interrelational- we've already said that in the paper mentioned above.⁹⁷ Charles Halpern⁹⁸ says: "Lawyers survive in a sea of interconnected relationships. Emotional intelligence (EQ) is absolutely necessary. Mindfulness builds the muscle of EQ".⁹⁹

In the papers titled "Mindfulness, Quantum Physics and "well-being is a two-way street"¹⁰⁰, "After COP26 Towards High Values etc"¹⁰¹, "Finding Ways to Be Lawyers in Today's World etc"¹⁰² we've written on the mindfulness's positive impact on lawyers.

Accessing a high consciousness through meditation is a way to awaken. Theory and research suggest that awakening and self-awareness are necessary to regulate one's behaviors, and for us it is clear what positive, zen, stress-free effect mindfulness, a form of present-centered, non-judgmental, and non-reactive awareness, has on behavioral self-regulation.

In our mindfulness practice we've found that traits mindfulness, particularly its nonjudging and non-reacting facets, predict good resilience, sustainability, persistence, creativity in difficult legal job. Mindfulness improves lawyers' self-regulation.

The origin of Consciousness is one of the great questions of our time. Different theories stem from physics, religion, philosophy, cognitive science etc. Various states of consciousness are associated with different brainwave patterns that can be altered and raised through meditation.

Neurobiology confirms that a physical process caused by the organization of energy in the brain is consciousness. Evidence from neurobiology indicates that the brain operates on the principle of energetic processing and that a certain organization of energy in the brain, measured with information theoretic techniques, can be reliably predict the presence and level of consciousness. Since energy is causally efficacious in physical systems, it is reasonable to claim that consciousness is in principle caused by energetic activity and how it is dynamically organized in the brain.

It is proposed that a particular kind of activity occurs in human brains that causes our conscious experience. It is a certain dynamic organization of energetic processes having a high degree of differentiation and integration. This organization is recursively self-referential and results in a pattern of energetic activity that blossoms to a degree of complexity sufficient for consciousness.¹⁰³

96 <https://libquotes.com/charlie-chaplin/quote/lbz3y8x>

97 Ibid

98 Charles Halpern is a lawyer, activist, author, educator, and meditation practitioner. He also served as the founding dean of CUNY School of Law, and as a faculty member of various prominent law schools across the country. Halpern is considered a pioneer in public interest law, responsible for various entrepreneurial and educational initiatives that contributed to legal, academic, social justice, and contemplative communities. He is founder of the Initiative for Mindfulness in Law (an innovative programme exploring the benefits of mindfulness to legal education and law practice at Berkley University, California) and one of the key thought-leaders for the mindfulness and law movement in the US, Halpern's book, *Making Waves and Riding the Currents: Activism and the Practice of Wisdom*, tells the story of how he brought public interest activism, mindfulness, and meditation into law schools and courthouses across the United States. https://greatergood.berkeley.edu/profile/charles_halpern

99 <https://www.theconsciouslawyer.co.uk/mindful-lawyering/>

100 Olga Nickole Kuyan. (2021). Mindfulness, Quantum Physics and "well-being is a two-way street". <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5732075>

101 Olga Nickole Kuyan. (2021). After COP26 Towards High Values. We don't Need To Change The World. Lawyers Step In. 10 Years after Lautsi v. Italy. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5732077>

102 Olga Nickole Kuyan. (2021). Finding Ways to Be Lawyers in Today's World, Calling to Have the Courage to Make Changes. Mindfulness Matters: Thought, Attention, Awakening. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5734445>

103 <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fpsyg.2018.02091/full>

We've called consciousness the fundamental cause of justice.¹⁰⁴ In the paper "Civil Justice, Discretion, Consciousness etc"¹⁰⁵ we've forwarded the idea that the level of his consciousness (the frequency of judge's thought/brain wave) is what makes the justice reality. We've based, *inter alia*, on well-established ideas from the complexity theory¹⁰⁶ and on the study published in Physical Review Research¹⁰⁷, potentially applicable to humans (to a judge/lawmaker/lawyer).

The research team studied the brain signals produced by 13 fruit flies both when they were awake and when they were anesthetized. They then analyzed the signals to see how complex they were. "We found the statistical complexity to be larger when a fly is awake than when the same fly is anesthetized," the team said. This is a major problem in justice, where it is crucial to differentiate between sleeping judges/lawyers and those who are awake. "The study is significant because it highlights an objective way to measure conscious arousal, based on well-established ideas from complexity theory," the team said. "It is potentially applicable to humans — and it reflects a growing interest in new theories of consciousness¹⁰⁸ that are experimentally testable."

This is especially important in the study of judiciary, judicial and law changes, and lawmakers/judges/lawyers, where complexity theory can offer insights into how courts/lawyers become more just (fair), accessible, sustainable, adaptive, and innovative. Faggin writes that the consciousness, which can also be called awareness, cannot exist inside the brain, where there are only biological and electromagnetic connections, it must exist from the beginning and be a quantum field.¹⁰⁹

This affirmation, however, must be proved, it takes a theory that explains the conscience, which demonstrates that conscience exists from the beginning, it is intrinsic and universal. Faggin takes quantum field theory (QFT) that can do that. The field is conscious, the particles are not as they are only "states of the fields".¹¹⁰

Justice is a part-whole with unique properties that identifies it. Quantum field theory tells us that physical reality is an undivided wholeness. The world is made of connected parts because there are no real boundaries between the parts and the whole. Within QFT, the fundamental entity is the quantum field, not a particle. An elementary particle does not exist as an object. It is instead an excited state of a quantum field. According to QFT, micro and macro worlds constitute levels of organizations of states of the quantum fields. These fields by interacting with each other create all that exists in the physical world. Each quantum field is a part-whole with unique properties that identifies it.

104 Olga Papkova. CIVIL JUSTICE DISCRETION CONSCIOUSNESS MINDFULNESS. Authorea. February 18, 2021. DOI: 10.22541/au.161360710.05001740/v1

105 Ibid

106 Complexity Theory allows us to better understand systems as diverse as cells, human beings, forest ecosystems, and organizations, that are only partially understood by traditional scientific methods (Zimmerman, B. Complexity Science: A Route through Hard Times and Uncertainty. Health Forum Journal 42-46 (March/April 1999); Zimmerman, B. Lindberg C. and Plsek P. Edgware: Insights from Complexity Science or Health Care Leaders. Irving Texas: VHA, Inc, (1998.). While it represents a relatively nascent field of study, it spans across a wide variety of disciplines in the physical, biological, and social sciences, and has profound implications for the way we think about and act within the world (Schneider, M&Somers,M. Organizations as complex adaptive systems: Implications of Complexity Theory for leadership research. The Leadership Quarterly, 17(4), 351–365(2006): <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.leafaqua.2006.04.006>).

107 *General anesthesia reduces complexity and temporal asymmetry of the informational structures derived from neural recordings in Drosophila* by Roberto N. Muñoz, Angus Leung, Aidan Zecevik, Felix A. Pollock, Dror Cohen, Bruno van Swinderen, Naotsugu Tsuchiya and Kavan Modiy, 22 May 2020, Physical Review Research.

108 Consciousness is to be awake, *inter alia*. <https://franciewhite.com/consciousness-cosmology-physics-definitions-terms-for-beginners/>

109 Ibid

110 <https://wsimag.com/science-and-technology/63570-the-nature-of-the-self>

In the paper titled “Civil Justice, Discretion, Consciousness, Mindfulness etc”¹¹¹ we’ve forwarded the idea that our true consciousness does not exist in our brains or in our bodies, but this illusion of our individual bodies has manifested the idea that we all think independently from one another, that judges/lawmakers/lawyers all think independently from one another. When we understand that there is a common spiritual bond between all things in the universe and that we are all part of a divine intelligence, that judges are all part of a cosmic Justice, this simple understanding will fill all the holes in modern civil justice included judicial discretion. A judge is just (fair) and his justice is immortal and timeless, once he identifies with the eternal reality the Higher Consciousness, and consistent with the quantum vision, he will enter the new paradigms of quantum consciousness.¹¹²

We’ve supposed that as minimum, a judge has to have legal consciousness with the tendency to raising it¹¹³.

In Justice, legal consciousness occupies the special place explained by the fact that it’s a source of justice together with legal norms and relevant institutions, moreover it acts as a part of mindfulness.

Legal consciousness is defined by Ewick and Silbey as the process by which people make sense of their experiences by relying on legal categories and concepts.¹¹⁴

Ivan Ilyin¹¹⁵ wrote: “Law needs legal consciousness in order to become a creative life force, and legal consciousness needs law in order to acquire a substantive basis and reality”.¹¹⁶

Legal consciousness is not conceivable without personality, without human spirituality, but it presupposes human respect for law. For the evil will and predatory instinct of legal deniers or selfish people, legal order are necessary as a “muzzle”.

“Legal consciousness is a collection of understood and/or imagined to have understood, legal awareness of ideas, views, feelings and traditions imbibed through legal socialization; which reflects as legal culture among given individual, or a group, or a given society at large. The legal consciousness evaluates the existing law and also bears in mind an image of the desired or ideal law” (Kaugia S).¹¹⁷

The Great Soviet Encyclopedia (1979) defined legal consciousness as “the sum of views and ideas expressing the attitude of people toward law, legality, and justice and their concept of what is lawful and unlawful. Legal consciousness is a form of social consciousness. Legal ideology, the system of legal views based on certain social and scientific viewpoints, is a concentrated expression of legal consciousness. The customs

111 Olga Papkova. CIVIL JUSTICE DISCRETION CONSCIOUSNESS MINDFULNESS. *Authorea*. February 18, 2021. DOI: [10.22541/au.161360710.05001740/v1](https://doi.org/10.22541/au.161360710.05001740/v1)

112 See: Valverde Raul, Quantum Consciousness & Spirit, *Journal of Consciousness Studies* 10(3):167-181 (April 2019).

113 Olga Papkova. CIVIL JUSTICE DISCRETION CONSCIOUSNESS MINDFULNESS. *Authorea*. February 18, 2021. DOI: [10.22541/au.161360710.05001740/v1](https://doi.org/10.22541/au.161360710.05001740/v1)

114 Ewick Patrizia; Silbey Susan, *The Common Place of Law: Stories from Everyday Life*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 22 (1998).

115 Ivan Alexandrovich Ilyin (1883–1954) is Russian philosopher and legal scholar. Although forbidden under the Soviet regime, Ilyin’s thoughts and works have come to be more and more appreciated over the last twenty years, especially since his earthly remains were re-interred in Russia in 2005. It is possible to say that he is the favourite Russian thinker of our times. Like all prophets, however, he was of course mainly ignored, unappreciated and even persecuted in his own times. Today, Ilyin is understood to be the voice of the faithful Russian emigration, a spiritual leader, a teacher, a prophet, a visionary preacher. His prophetic insights have been justified since the fall of Communism and the huge interest in his works there now. Ilyin, who died over half a century ago, is the prophet of the new Russia which is being born and which alone can give the contemporary world a viable future, providing that it is given time to grow to fruition in contemporary Russia. One of the problems he worked on was the question: what has eventually led Russia to the tragedy of the revolution?

116 Ilyin, I.A. О сущности правосознания, (On the essence of legal consciousness), Moscow, Volume I, 99 (1993).

117 <https://www.juridicainternational.eu/index.php?id=12433>

and feelings of people in relation to legal phenomena constitute the psychological aspect of legal consciousness" ¹¹⁸

The purpose of raising legal consciousness to higher consciousness is to become more aware of who you are and how you show up and then act consciously. "Self-knowledge is like lost innocence; however unsettling you find it, it can never be 'unthought' or 'unknown'," - Sandel says. ¹¹⁹ With a higher consciousness, taking responsible action becomes easier. You become conscious of your behaviors and can more consciously choose how to treat yourself and others.

For us the justice is found in the personality of a lawmaker\judge, not in being judge\lawmaker separate from other judges\lawmakers and possessing their own needs or goals, rights and responsibilities: the individuality of a lawmaker\judge is such for a purely career\education and social fact; but justice is his inner truth, his vocation, the purpose of his entire existence, emerge only when he sets out to become a personality, realizing his own ontological potential, which is extra-natural and participates in the Universe, in Higher Consciousness. We've already sought to forward this idea. ¹²⁰

Let us turn again to M. Norbekov ¹²¹: to the provocative titles of his books ¹²², to the deep interesting content of his method ¹²³, and to his excellent results ¹²⁴. In his "Key to Insight", he explains in detail that first you need to learn to smile, rejoice and be content, and then health, wealth, and love will come. But not vice versa ! The formula "Give first, and then I will be satisfied" does not work. Following this theory first a judge\lawmaker needs to learn to be just, to be in justice and then justice will come.

Here we invite you to apply the Holonomic brain theory, also known as The Holographic Brain, a specific theory of quantum consciousness. ¹²⁵ It describes human cognition by modeling the brain as a holographic storage network. ¹²⁶

Following this theory and these ideas the separation between judges, between court and key figures of a trial, like the separation between particles, as between everything that makes up the universe, is an illusion. Reality is the greatest illusion than we can imagine. Justice-reality is the illusion. Everything that surrounds us is the result of a frequency, so if the frequency is changed the structure of matter changes in turn.

In 1982, the French physicist Alain Aspect ¹²⁷, director of the CNRS, carried out an extremely important experiment: he noticed that by subjecting some subatomic particles (in this case electrons) to certain conditions, they were able to communicate simultaneously regardless of the distance that separated them (millimeters or billions of kilometers); the subatomic particles were somehow connected in a non-local way. This experiment intrigued the British physicist David Bohm, who understood that the separation between particles, as between everything that makes up the universe, is an illusion. At a

118 <https://encyclopedia2.thefreedictionary.com/Legal+Consciousness>

119 Michael J. Sandel, Justice: What's the Right Thing to Do?

https://www.goodreads.com/author/quotes/90763.Michael_J_Sandel

120 Ibid.

121 Professor Mirzakarim Norbekov has a doctor's degree in psychology, pedagogy and medicine philosophy. He is a member of several international academies, a developer of patented inventions and a best-seller author. He is an ardent martial artist with a black belt and a third Dan in Karate.

122 Опыт дурака 1, или Ключ к прозрению Опыт duraka 1, ili Klyuch k prozreniyu (Russian) – Fool's experience or Key to Insight (January 1, 2019)

123 The method by which Prof. Norbekov has helped countless people to heal themselves is based on a thousand-year old Eastern doctrine, Sufism. It builds on the knowledge that man, as a unity of body, mind and soul, has astounding inner potentials, which he can activate at any time.

124 In the case of diseases, man can bring his soul back into harmony with its true nature, and thus heal himself.

125 It was developed by neuroscientist Karl Pribram initially in collaboration with physicist David Bohm building on the initial theories of Holograms originally formulated by Dennis Gabor.

126 Forsdyke D. R, Samuel Butler and human long term memory: Is the cupboard bare?, Journal of Theoretical Biology. 258 (1): 156–164 (2009); Andrew A. M. The decade of the brain - further thoughts, Kybernetes. 26 (3): 255–264 (1997)

127 Alain Aspect (1947) is a French physicist noted for his experimental work on quantum entanglement.

deeper level of reality and vibrations "everything is connected with everything", particles exist as extensions of the same "fundamental organism". Everything appears separate to us because we are able to perceive only a certain level of reality, so the universe itself is an immense projection, a hologram.

Many scientists now believe the brain and body operate on holographic principles on the cellular, molecular, and neural levels. Holographic theory helps us to understand social sciences systems, *inter alia*, Justice system by stressing the wholeness of the system. Individual components of a system cannot be manipulated without affecting all other components in the system.

Quantum physics, albeit using a different terminology, expresses the same concept that the ancient masters were aware of: everything is one. Our universe, in fact, can be defined as a gigantic hologram.¹²⁸

Living cells are quantum systems, not classical system. Their essential interdependence with the environment is another clue that they have not lost their individual connection with the wholeness of the quantum fields.

In a holistic system, a separate part cannot exist. A holistic system is not the sum of its apparent parts. Holism means that the whole is more than the sum of the "parts". In other words, in the definition of what we call reality, we have that irreducible and infinite portion that behind the scenes plays a fundamental role in quantum physics as well as in all living systems.

In the paper titled "Social Values in Europe etc"¹²⁹, we have stated that men's realities interconnect, causing the essential changes in the society, in Consciousness itself. We expect that the consciousness of a judge/lawyer/politician/any human being has exponentially higher comprehension than the sum of the comprehensions of its elementary parts because, when two or more lower-level conscious entities form a higher-level entity, its new consciousness is an integrated part-whole far more complex than the sum of the components' consciousness.

Our Justice system can be defined as a hologram. According to the best theory of Alessandro Fedrizzi, Professor of Quantum Physics, Heriot-Watt University, and Massimiliano Proietti, the facts can actually be subjective.¹³⁰ The new picture of the world order, presented by French-British scientists, admits the complete absence of objective reality. According to this theory, the universe is a hologram woven by myriads of minds. The same thing can be said regarding Justice: the Justice is a hologram woven by minds. "Only if we can see the universe as a whole in which each part reflects the totality and in which the great beauty lies in its diversity, will we begin to understand who we are and where we are,"¹³¹ - says Terzani¹³². "But personality is not part of the universe, the universe is a part of personality, it is its quality. Such is the paradox of personalism",¹³³ - Berdyaev¹³⁴ wrote.

128 Holography is simply a photographic technique that allows us to obtain three-dimensional images by superimposing light waves diffused by an object hit by a laser beam with others diffused by the same laser source. And reflected with a mirror; a hologram, in essence, is a 3D photograph produced with the support of a laser beam and a photographic film on which information is recorded. The peculiar characteristic of a hologram is that each portion of the whole contains the complete holographic image, each tiny fragment therefore contains a smaller, but intact, version of that image (even if the resolution of this image is proportional to the size of the fragment).

129 Olga Nickole Papkova Kuyan. Social Values in Europe. Protecting Freedom of Thought, Conscience, Religion, Creating What?: Justice, Sophia, Phronesis. Authorea. July 14, 2021.
DOI: 10.22541/au.162626095.53333722/v1

130 <https://theconversation.com/quantum-physics-our-study-suggests-objective-reality-doesnt-exist-126805>

131 Terzani Tiziano, *La fine è il mio inizio* (2006)

132 Tiziano Terzani (1938 – 2004) was an Italian journalist and writer, best known for his extensive knowledge of 20th century East Asia and for being one of the very few western reporters to witness both the fall of Saigon to the hands of the Viet Cong and the fall of Phnom Penh at the hands of the Khmer Rouge in the mid-1970s.

133 Berdyaev N. *Slavery and Freedom.* , 22, (1939)

134 Nikolai Alexandrovich Berdyaev (1874 – 1948) was a Russian philosopher, theologian, and Christian existentialist who emphasized the existential spiritual significance of human freedom and the human person.

Francisco Di biase¹³⁵ proposes a quantum-informational holographic model of brain-consciousness-universe interactions based in the holonomic neural networks¹³⁶ of Karl Pribram¹³⁷, in the holographic quantum theory developed by David Bohm¹³⁸, and in the non-locality property of the quantum field¹³⁹ described by Hiroomi Umezawa¹⁴⁰. Francisco Di biase considers this model an extension of the interactive dualism of Sir John Eccles¹⁴¹, of an interconnection between brain and spirit by means of quantum microsites named dendrons and psychons.¹⁴² The scientist proposes a dynamic concept of consciousness seen as a holoinformational flux interconnecting the holonomic informational quantum brain dynamics, with the quantum informational holographic nature of the universe.¹⁴³ This self-organizing flux is generated by the holographic mode of treatment of neuronal information and can be optimized through practices of deep meditation, prayer, and others states of higher consciousness that underlie the coherence of cerebral waves. In brain mapping studies performed during the occurrence of these harmonic states we can see the spectral array of brain waves highly synchronized and perfectly ordered like a unique harmonic wave, as if all frequencies of all neurons from all cerebral centers played the same symphony. This highly coherent brain state generates the non-local holographic informational cortical field of consciousness that interconnect the human brain and the holographic cosmos.

The comprehension of this holonomic quantum informational nature of brain-consciousness-universe interconnectedness allows us to solve the mind-matter problem, the Justice problem unifying science, philosophy, and spiritual traditions in a more transdisciplinary, holistic, integrated paradigm. In this new arrangement cosmovision, consciousness and transpersonal phenomena becomes part of Science and of the very holoinformational nature of the Holographic Conscious Multiverse.

We give birth to wind. We share the Faggini's thought that we are fields of fields, we are conscious, we are never the same. The living organism is a quantum organism, life is a quantum field as quantum biology can demonstrate, but we have to wait for it to develop. The state of a quantum field is a private state, it cannot be cloned, it is the internal state of that system¹⁴⁴

In the paper titled "Finding Ways to Be Lawyers etc"¹⁴⁵ we've written that legal style of life is to remain in constant flux. Being lawyer is being in movement. Being lawyer means the

135 https://www.academia.edu/44055993/Toward_A_Computational_Theory_of_Everything

136 http://www.scholarpedia.org/article/Holonomic_brain_theory

137 Karl H. Pribram (1919 – 2015) was a professor at Georgetown University, an emeritus professor of psychology and psychiatry at Stanford University and distinguished professor at Radford University. Board-certified as a neurosurgeon, Pribram did pioneering work on the definition of the limbic system, the relationship of the frontal cortex to the limbic system, the sensory-specific "association" cortex of the parietal and temporal lobes, and the classical motor cortex of the human brain. He worked with Karl Lashley at the Yerkes Primate Center of which he was to become director later. To the general public, Pribram is best known for his development of the holonomic brain model of cognitive function and his contribution to ongoing neurological research into memory, emotion, motivation and consciousness.

138 <https://futurism.com/david-bohm-and-the-holographic-universe>

139 https://www.researchgate.net/publication/259458796_Hiroomi_Umezawa_and_Quantum_Field_Theory

140 Hiroomi Umezawa (1924 – 1995) was a physicist and Distinguished Professor in the Department of Physics at the University of Wisconsin–Milwaukee and later at the University of Alberta. He is known for his fundamental contributions to quantum field theory and for his work on quantum phenomena in relation to the mind.

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/253538121_A_HOLOINFORMATIONAL_MODEL_OF_CONSCIOUSNESS_-_Quantum_Biosystems_2009_3_207-220

141 Sir John Carew Eccles (1903 – 1997) was an Australian neurophysiologist and philosopher who won the 1963 Nobel Prize in Physiology or Medicine for his work on the synapse. He shared the prize with Andrew Huxley and Alan Lloyd Hodgkin.

142 https://www.researchgate.net/publication/289745276_HOLOINFORMATIONAL_CONSCIOUSNESS_An_extension_of_Interactive_Dualism_with_Anticipatory_Parameters_-_International_Journal_of_Computing_Anticipatory_Systems_Vol22_314-330_2008

143 https://nah.sen.es/vmfiles/abstract/NAHV1N42013162_168EN.pdf

144 <https://www.millionaire.it/federico-faggini-ho-inventato-il-microchip-ma-il-computer-piu-forte-e-il-cervello-umano/>

movement and doesn't mean certain working conditions; means the pathway and doesn't mean a harbor.¹⁴⁶ That's why consciousness is the personal experience.

Let's use some ideas. Schrödinger teaches us: "Consciousness is the theater, and precisely the only theater on which everything that takes place in the universe is represented, the container that contains everything, absolutely everything, and outside of which there is nothing."¹⁴⁷

...“Hence this life of yours which you are living is not merely a piece of the entire existence, but is in a certain sense the whole; only this whole is not so constituted that it can be surveyed in one single glance. This, as we know, is what the Brahmins express in that sacred, mystic formula which is yet really so simple and so clear: Tat tvam asi, this is you. Or, again, in such words as 'I am in the east and in the west, I am below and above, I am this whole world'.”¹⁴⁸

Einstein with the theory of "unified field theory"¹⁴⁹, affirms that a single original and undifferentiated energy is the creator of all forms of matter. Einstein¹⁵⁰ and other scientists have often marveled at the so-called "parallelism between thought and physical laws"¹⁵¹, that is, at the fact that natural laws can be expressed in logical-mathematical terms. This means that objective reality and subjective thought arise from a single principle.

Subatomic physics¹⁵² speaks of energy fields, which vibrate or propagate by waves, nothing solid and still exists and what we see as "solid" is the result of this movement.

E. Schrodinger writes: “consciousness is a singular of which the plural is unknown; that there is only one thing and that what seems to be a plurality is merely a series of different aspects of this one thing, produced by a deception.”¹⁵³

Thirty years later: “There is obviously only one alternative, namely the unification of minds or consciousnesses. Their multiplicity is only apparent, in truth there is only one mind.”¹⁵⁴

And thirty six years later, shortly before his death, he writes again (as a comment to a line in Upanishads):“...the plurality of sensitive beings is mere appearance (maya); in reality they are all only aspects of the one being.”¹⁵⁵

The universe in its essence is energy and all of reality is like this, everything obeys the laws of quantum physics, which manifest an intrinsic order which reveals the existence of a kind of deep intelligence.

145 Olga Nickole Kuyan. (2021). Finding Ways to Be Lawyers in Today's World, Calling to Have the Courage to Make Changes. Mindfulness Matters: Thought, Attention, Awakening. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5734445>

146 Ibid.

147 <https://www.istc.cnr.it/en/personalpage/gb-resources-others-thoughts>

148 <https://www.goodreads.com/quotes/6672441-hence-this-life-of-yours-which-you-are-living-is>

149 According to the modern discoveries in physics, forces are not transmitted directly between interacting objects, but instead are described and interrupted by intermediary entities called fields.

Classically, however, a duality of the fields is combined into a single physical field. For over a century, unified field theory has remained an open line of research and the term was coined by Albert Einstein, who attempted to unify his general theory of relativity with electromagnetism. The "Theory of Everything" and Grand Unified Theory are closely related to unified field theory, but differ by not requiring the basis of nature to be fields, and often by attempting to explain physical constants of nature. The goal of a unified field theory has led to a great deal of progress for future theoretical physics and progress continues.

150 “Imagination is more important than knowledge,” Einstein would say. <https://evernote.com/blog/einsteins-unique-approach-to-thinking/>

151 In the philosophy of mind, psychophysical parallelism (or simply parallelism) is the theory that mental and bodily events are perfectly coordinated, without any causal interaction between them.

152 In physical sciences, a subatomic particle is a particle that is smaller than an atom.

153 Schrödinger E, What is Life? with Mind and Matter and Autobiographical Sketches. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 29 (1993). (Original editions: What is Life?, Cambridge, 1944, Mind and Matter, Cambridge, 1956)

154 Opt. Cit, 129.

155 Schrödinger E, My View of the World. Ox Bow Press, Woodbridge, Conn., 101 (1983) (original German edition: Meine Weltansicht, Paul Zsolnay Verlag, Wien 1961). This book includes two essays, *Seek for the Road*, written 1925, and *What is Real?*, written 1960.

Michio Kaku¹⁵⁶ recently caused a small shock in the scientific community by claiming to have found evidence of the existence of an unknown and intelligent force that governs nature. "I came to the conclusion that we are in a world made up of rules created by an intelligence, not very different from a computer game, but of course, more complex," said the scientist.¹⁵⁷

David Bohm hypothesizes two levels of human consciousness, one that makes us see a portion of reality and a deeper level where everything is connected in a kind of continuous wholeness, a kind of global consciousness that unites us all, especially when there is a strong thought common to many people, but not only is there a type of consciousness in all things that develop following this kind of program.¹⁵⁸

Bohm was deeply interested in exploring the nature of consciousness, with particular attention to the role of thought as it relates to attention, motivation, and conflict in the individual and in society.¹⁵⁹

Max Planck says: "All matter originates and exists only by virtue of a force which brings the particle of an atom to vibration and holds this most minute solar system of the atom together. We must assume behind this force the existence of a conscious and intelligent mind. This mind is the matrix of all matter."¹⁶⁰

Carl Jung talks about a collective memory to which we are all unconsciously connected¹⁶¹. So our task is to feel part of the whole creation, enveloped by an energy greater than us, connected to an immense history, where even a little story of everybody of us is precious and powerful, because pregnant with High Intelligence, High Consciousness: "Christ could be born a thousand times in Bethlehem – but all in vain until He is born in me,"¹⁶²- Angelus Silesius¹⁶³ says.

Following Amir D. Aczel¹⁶⁴ let's take an atom (composed of a center with protons and neutrons surrounded by a cloud of orbiting electrons). If one of its electrons loses two "units" of energy, approaching the nucleus, the atom emits two photons, or two particles of light, which, while moving away from each other, remain entangled. In what sense? If, after an indefinite period of time, one of the two photons is deflected, the other also suffers the same fate, albeit light years away.

It seems incredible that the slightest action on a particle immediately affects the twin particle even if it has been sent a universe away. Yet this extraordinary property seems to be an unavoidable feature of the most accredited and powerful theory of physics we have today: quantum mechanics. Known by the technical term of "entanglement", an interweaving of particles, it constitutes the greatest challenge for physicists, philosophers and social sciences since Werner Heisenberg began to plumb the mysteries of the infinitely small.

156 Michio Kaku (January 24, 1947) is an American theoretical physicist, a professor of theoretical physics in the City College of New York and CUNY Graduate Center. He is famous for formulating the revolutionary string theory (model of fundamental physics which assumes that apparently specific material particles are actually "vibrational states"). He has written the New York Times best sellers *Physics of the Impossible* (2008), *Physics of the Future* (2011), and *The Future of the Mind* (2014).

157 <https://www.nbcnews.com/mach/science/michio-kaku-sees-amazing-things-our-future-except-those-scary-ncna851226>

158 More details: Scaruffi Piero. *The Nature of Consciousness* (2006)

159 See David Bohm, *Thought as a System*, Psychology Press (1994)

160 Planck Max, in *Archimedes to Hawking: Laws of Science and the Great Minds Behind Them*, Oxford University Press, 417 (19 March 2008)

161 A collective unconscious, term introduced by psychiatrist Carl Jung to represent a form of the unconscious (that part of the mind containing memories and impulses of which the individual is not aware) common to mankind as a whole and originating in the inherited structure of the brain.

162 As quoted in *Messenger Of The Heart: The Book Of Angelus Silesius, With Observations By Frederick Franck* (2005)

163 Angelus Silesius (1624 – 1677), born Johann Scheffler, also known as the Prophet of the Ineffable, was a German mystic of the Catholic Church, as well as a poet, priest and physician.

164 Aczel Amir D, *Entanglement: The Greatest Mystery in Physics* (September 18, 2002)

Using the science of very little things, Federico Faggin, has proposed an explanation of the reality. Again with pleasure we leave the field to the scientist expert in microtechnology, father of the digital revolution, who invented two of the pillars of the digital revolution, the microprocessor and the touch screen.

F.Faggin asks for attention to the small details of life and to what surpasses us infinitely.

He asks for consciousness and attention, to read the history as a womb of births.

He asks for a attentive heart, to watch over the sprouts, over what is emerging, the new that is born, the first steps of peace, the breath of light that is drawn on the wall of the night or the crisis, the first cries of life and its shoots.

"I don't know what will happen, but I hope people will learn to cooperate instead of competing. Cooperation is essential to tackle climate change, corruption and poverty at a planetary level. We're people, not machines, and what makes us different are our conscience and values. Let's hope we always remember that."¹⁶⁵ Federico Faggin says.

He invites us to a twofold attention: to reality and to infinity. Reality is within the infinite and the infinite is within reality; the eternal shines in the instant and the instant insinuates itself into the eternal.

Faggin wants to demonstrate what consciousness is and to do it scientifically. It is an important purpose because it means that what makes us human is part of science, that is, that spirituality is a dimension that can be analyzed with the theory of quantum fields.

This theory says that all reality is made up of quantum fields, including us. These fields are united in a basic, original and all-encompassing field, the Whole. Until now, the Whole had never been analyzed. Now we know that it is a quantum field and it is a universal, all-encompassing, unique and basic consciousness.

Qualia. Our personal experience has the value of truth, because it is personal, unique and involves the whole person, it gives a sense of unity - the thing that quantum says - so we can say that we are a quantum field and that consciousness is something original. Consciousness is the ability to have an experience of sensations and feelings that neurologists call "qualia".¹⁶⁶

Here we argue that consciousness itself is primary and qualia form the foundation of experience. We share the arguments of the new science, tying objects that are being perceived to the subjective experience, through the units of subjective experience called qualia. "Qualia are often referred to as the phenomenal properties of experience, and experiences that have qualia are referred to as being phenomenally conscious."¹⁶⁷

In the essay titled "What is consciousness?", Faggin has stated that the existence of qualia is not explainable based on the current scientific theories. He has also argued that the capacity to comprehend seems to be even more difficult to explain than qualia.¹⁶⁸

We share the steps to fully develop the science of qualia.¹⁶⁹ Our view is a natural continuation of the quantum world view.

¹⁶⁵ <https://www.domusweb.it/en/news/2021/05/21/federico-faggin-were-people-machines-will-not-replace-us.html>

¹⁶⁶ In philosophy of mind, qualia are defined as individual instances of subjective, conscious experience. The term qualia derives from the Latin neuter plural form (qualia): meaning "of what sort" or "of what kind" in a specific instance, such as "what it is like to taste a specific apple, this particular apple now". Various philosophers emphasize or deny the existence of certain features of qualia. Consequently, the nature and existence of various definitions of qualia remain controversial. While some philosophers of mind like Daniel Dennett argue that qualia do not exist and are incompatible with neuroscience and naturalism, some neuroscientists and neurologists like Gerald Edelman, Antonio Damasio, Vilayanur Ramachandran, Giulio Tononi, Christof Koch and Rodolfo Llinás state that qualia exist and that the desire to eliminate them is based on an erroneous interpretation on the part of some philosophers regarding what constitutes science.

¹⁶⁷ <https://iep.utm.edu/qualia/>

¹⁶⁸ <http://www.fagginfoundation.org/articles/the-nature-of-consciousness/>

¹⁶⁹ See inter alia: Chopra, D., Kafatos, M.C. (2014) From Quanta to Qualia: How a Paradigm Shift Turns Into Science. Philosophy Study Vol. 4, Number 4, pp. 287-301.

"The.. quantum properties reflect the consciousness of the quantum fields and become integrated into hierarchical structures that increase the level of consciousness of the entire living organism in ways we have yet to understand,"¹⁷⁰- Fuggin writes. He hypothesizes that consciousness is a fundamental property of the quantum fields not yet acknowledged by physics.¹⁷¹ It constitutes the greatest challenge for us here.

Personal consciousnesses which are all only aspects of the one being can be called the fundamental cause of justice – we forward this idea.

If a judge uses mindful discretion, the minds of trial's figures may be forced to choose one probability and that's the state the judge observes.

In 1920, Niels Bohr¹⁷² and others developed the Copenhagen Interpretation¹⁷³, stating that a quantum particle doesn't exist in one state or another (as a wave or as a particle), but in all of its possible states at once. When we observe its state, the particle is forced to choose one probability, and that's the state we observe. The particle may be forced into a different observable state each time, which explains why a particle behaves erratically and can give differing results.

The "observer effect"¹⁷⁴ states that the process of observing a particle changes the way the particle behaves. Following this way we could say that the judge leading the procedure changes the way the trial figures behave.

When we put these together and add mindfulness into the mix by taking into account the role of consciousness on the matter (energy) around us, we get an interesting set of theories.

Wolfgang Pauli¹⁷⁵ was famous for what became known as the "Pauli effect," which manifested in the spontaneous breakdown of laboratory equipment whenever he entered the room. It also manifested in other ways, including mischievous events like chairs collapsing and train cars decoupling, to the detriment of those around him, but not to himself.

At one point in his life he collaborated with psychiatrist Carl Jung to study synchronicity, in part because of the "coincidences" surrounding his effect on matter. Not surprisingly, he believed in psychokinesis—the influencing of matter by thought—and that parapsychology was worthy of study. In fact, he was one of the first to consider and explore "quantum metaphysics," although Max Planck, the "father" of quantum physics, also believed in the metaphysical. Planck said, "I regard consciousness as fundamental. I regard matter as derivative from consciousness. We cannot get behind consciousness. Everything that we talk about, everything that we regard as existing, postulates consciousness."¹⁷⁶

With these theories the spiritual enters the world of justice.

170 <http://www.fagginfoundation.org/articles/the-nature-of-consciousness/>

171 Ibid

172 Niels Henrik David Bohr (1885 – 1962) was a Danish physicist. He received the Nobel Prize for Physics in 1922 for his contributions which were essential to modern understandings of atomic structure and quantum mechanics.

173 The Copenhagen interpretation is the earliest and most widespread interpretation of quantum mechanics. It is inspired by the works carried out in the Danish capital by Niels Bohr and Werner Heisenberg, mainly, around 1927 and concerns the theory of quantum measurement, the principle of complementarity and wave-particle duality.

In particular, the two scholars extended the probabilistic interpretation of the wave function proposed by Max Born, considering meaningless questions about the values of the quantities of a physical system before it is measured, as the measurement process randomly extracts one of the values allowed by the wave function that describes the quantum state of the system. This interpretation has received a better defined formulation since the 1950s, mainly thanks to Wolfgang Pauli. The expression "Copenhagen Interpretation" was introduced by Heisenberg in 1955.

174 <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8423983>

175 Wolfgang Pauli (1900-1958), an Austrian-Swiss physicist, won the Nobel Prize in physics in 1945 for the "Pauli Principle" involving spin theory.

176 <https://www.aaas.org/quantum-mechanics-and-consciousness-connection#:~:text=Planck%20said%2C%20%22I%20regard%20matter,be%20explained%20by%20quantum%20mechanics.>

The way of justice. “I think I can safely say that nobody understands quantum mechanics.”¹⁷⁷ It is one of the most repeated quotes of Richard Feynman.¹⁷⁸

Neils Bohr once said concerning the quantum world: “Those who are not shocked when they first come across quantum theory cannot possibly have understood it. Anyone who is not shocked by quantum theory has not understood a single word. If you think you can talk about quantum theory without feeling dizzy, you haven't understood the first thing about it.”¹⁷⁹ The dance of life is so tentative and crazy that it leads physicists to wonder if anything real exists at all.¹⁸⁰

Now physicists know that electrons are in a state of frenzied activity and the world of the atom is in a state of violent quantum fluctuations. In quantum physics, a quantum fluctuation (or vacuum state fluctuation or vacuum fluctuation)¹⁸¹ is the temporary random change in the amount of energy in a point in space, as prescribed by Werner Heisenberg¹⁸²'s uncertainty principle¹⁸³. This principle states that contrary to our intuition vacuum is not empty but contains temporary changes in the amount of energy in a point in space.¹⁸⁴

Ernest Rutherford¹⁸⁵ proved that an atom was made of mostly empty space with a tiny, dense, positively-charged nucleus. Based on these results, Rutherford proposed the nuclear model of the atom.¹⁸⁶ Atoms are filled with electrons. It's true that a large percentage of the atom's mass is concentrated in its tiny nucleus, but that does not imply that the rest of the atom is empty. The content is not empty, ever. Also Torricelli, removing the air from a bottle, shows that inside the bottle there are still many physical entities: electric and magnetic fields, and a continuous swarm of quantum particles.¹⁸⁷

177 <https://www.facebook.com/watch/?v=967586087044967>

178 Richard Phillips Feynman (1918 – 1988) was an American theoretical physicist, known for his work in the path integral formulation of quantum mechanics, the theory of quantum electrodynamics, the physics of the superfluidity of supercooled liquid helium, as well as his work in particle physics for which he proposed the parton model. For contributions to the development of quantum electrodynamics, Feynman received the Nobel Prize in Physics in 1965 jointly with Julian Schwinger and Shin'ichirō Tomonaga.

179 https://en.wikiquote.org/wiki/Niels_Bohr

180 See above.

181 See in detail: Álvaro G. López, On an electrodynamic origin of quantum fluctuations (2020), arXiv:2001.07392

182 Werner Karl Heisenberg (1901 – 1976) was a German theoretical physicist and one of the key pioneers of quantum mechanics. He is known for the uncertainty principle, which he published in 1927. Heisenberg was awarded the 1932 Nobel Prize in Physics "for the creation of quantum mechanics"

183 Heisenberg's uncertainty principle is a key principle in quantum mechanics. Very roughly, it states that if we know everything about where a particle is located (the uncertainty of position is small), we know nothing about its momentum (the uncertainty of momentum is large), and vice versa. Versions of the uncertainty principle also exist for other quantities as well, such as energy and time. <https://www.britannica.com/science/uncertainty-principle>

184 See in detail: <https://www.sciencedaily.com/releases/2018/08/180820113053.htm>

185 Ernest Rutherford (1871 –1937) was a New Zealand-born British physicist who came to be known as the father of nuclear physics. In early work, Rutherford discovered the concept of radioactive half-life, the radioactive element radon, and differentiated and named alpha and beta radiation. This work was performed at McGill University in Montreal, Quebec, Canada. It is the basis for the Nobel Prize in Chemistry he was awarded in 1908 "for his investigations into the disintegration of the elements, and the chemistry of radioactive substances".

186 <https://www.khanacademy.org/science/chemistry/electronic-structure-of-atoms/history-of-atomic-structure/a/discovery-of-the-electron-and-nucleus>

187 Torricelli's experiment was invented in Pisa in 1643 by the Italian scientist Evangelista Torricelli (1608-1647), an Italian physicist and mathematician, and a student of Galileo. He is best known for his invention of the barometer.

In the paper titled "Civil Justice, Discretion, Consciousness, Mindfulness etc"¹⁸⁸, following the ideas of Nagarjuna¹⁸⁹, J.L.Garfield¹⁹⁰, Carlo Rovelli¹⁹¹, we've put into discussion that Justice has no existence in itself and Justice as the content is not empty, ever¹⁹².

Starting from the Nāgārjuna's: "Emptiness¹⁹³ [is] the essence of compassion"¹⁹⁴ we've supposed that Emptiness (no-Justice) is the essence of Justice; and we've put this into discussion.

In the paper¹⁹⁵ we've affirmed that the doctrine of emptiness¹⁹⁶ (no-self) as conceived in particular by Carlo Rovelli, who takes it directly from the teachings of Buddhist monk Nāgārjuna is identical to the way that lawyers have of conceiving justice.

Justice is dharma¹⁹⁷. "All dharmas are characterized by emptiness". *Inter alia*, "dharman characterizes those personal actions that generate or maintain the cosmic order".¹⁹⁸ Ultimately the term Dharma rises to the meaning of "truth" and "justice".

In our paper we were sure that a common opinion among lawyers who deal with justice is "Justice is characterized by emptiness".

In today's world there is still much controversy going on about the access to justice; the reality of justice¹⁹⁹. If we see access to justice as reality (as human right)²⁰⁰, the same

188 Olga Papkova. CIVIL JUSTICE DISCRETION CONSCIOUSNESS MINDFULNESS. Authorea. February 18, 2021. DOI: 10.22541/au.161360710.05001740/v1

189 Nāgārjuna (c. 150 – c. 250 CE) is widely considered one of the most important Buddhist philosophers. The term used by Nagarjuna to describe this lack of self-essence is "emptiness" (sunyata): things are "empty" in the sense that they have no autonomous reality, they exist thanks to, as a function of, with respect to, from the perspective of something. On the other hand Nagarjuna distinguishes two levels, as do so many philosophy and science: conventional reality, apparent, with its illusory or perspective aspects, and ultimate reality. But it takes this distinction in a surprising direction: the ultimate reality, the essence is absence, emptiness.

190 Jay L. Garfield describes that Nāgārjuna approached causality from the four noble truths and dependent origination. Nāgārjuna distinguished two dependent origination views in a causal process, that which causes effects and that which causes conditions. This is predicated in the two truth doctrine, as conventional truth and ultimate truth held together, in which both are empty in existence. The distinction between effects and conditions is controversial. In Nāgārjuna's approach, cause means an event or state that has power to bring an effect. (Garfield, Jay L, Dependent Arising and the Emptiness of Emptiness: Why Did Nāgārjuna Start with Causation?, Philosophy East and West. 44 (2): 219–50 (April 1994)

191 Carlo Rovelli is an internationally renowned theoretical physicist who during his career has worked mainly in the field of quantum gravity and was one of the founders of the theory of loop quantum gravity. Carlo Rovelli also deals with the history and philosophy of science. In *Helgoland* Rovelli delves into revolutionary theory, first allowing us to understand its theoretical and practical value, and then exploring the issues that make quantum theory one of the most mysterious physical theories science has to do with. These mysteries have been at the center of the research of physicists, philosophers and other great thinkers for years: Rovelli focuses on the relational interpretation and on the links between this interpretation and oriental history, art, literature and philosophy. The author leads to discover how this view of quantum theory can lead us to reconsider the way in which we think about reality.

192 Because *nothing has existence in itself*.

193 Śūnyatā could be translated as vacuity, and sometimes voidness, also. A common translation is "no-self", without a self, the Pāli Canon (The Pāli Canon or Tipitaka is the oldest collection of Buddhist canonical texts. It is the pillar of Theravāda Buddhism and is currently practiced in Burma, Thailand, Cambodia, Laos and Sri Lanka. See in details: Lewis R. Lancaster in Buddhist Literature: Canonization, Encyclopedia of Religion, 331-6 (1986)) uses anattā as a singular substantive, meaning "not-self"(See; Bronkhorst, Johannes, Buddhist Teaching in India, Wisdom Publications, 124 (2009).

194 "Śūnyatā karuṇā garbham"

195 Olga Papkova. CIVIL JUSTICE DISCRETION CONSCIOUSNESS MINDFULNESS. Authorea. February 18, 2021. DOI: 10.22541/au.161360710.05001740/v1

196 Śūnyatā (tr.eng. Emptiness) is a feminine noun of the Sanskrit. which indicates one of the fundamental doctrines in Buddhism. See: <http://sanskritdictionary.com/?q=%C5%9B%C5%ABnyat%C4%81&iencoding=&lang>

197 "Dharma" is a term that refers to many meanings, among which the main ones are: 1) teaching a systematic knowledge; 2) conducted according to justice; 3) causal condition; 4) phenomenon, effect; 5) ultimate Reality (Tathata).

198 Mahony, William K. Hinduism, Encyclopedia of Religions, vol. 9: "Hindu Dharma". Milan, Jaca Book (2006).

199 <https://www.idlo.int/fr/news/highlights/story-rosie-reality-access-justice> ; https://www.abajournal.com/magazine/article/alternative_facts_law_justice_reality ; <https://ncsc.contentdm.oclc.org/digital/collection/accessfair/id/153> etc

200 <https://www.eui.eu/DepartmentsAndCentres/Law/Publications/Books/Francioni/AccessToJustice>

justice should be reality. All of reality is interaction.²⁰¹ Justice is interaction.²⁰² In fact, the Buddha affirmed that all things are empty of intrinsic existence, that is, that all things exist not by themselves but because they are in relation to something else; quantum physics essentially says the same thing and that is that objects appear to exist only when they affect other objects.

Justice should be achieved²⁰³ in every case, for individual parties (person or group). Civil Trial is the Civil Procedural Relations. Interaction (Civil Justice) is different from Civil Procedural Relations in trial. The difference is that Civil Justice is the situation or occurrence in which two or more key figures or events act upon one another to produce a Civil Justice effect; the effect resulting from such a situation or occurrence while civil procedural relation is the manner in which key figures may be associated. Civil Justice is the content, Civil Procedural Relations are the form.

In the paper titled "Civil Justice, Discretion, Consciousness, Mindfulness etc"²⁰⁴ to conceptualize Justice as interaction we've utilized the Complex Thinking²⁰⁵ concept and Mead's theory²⁰⁶.

Following "two truths theory"²⁰⁷ in Buddhism - conventional and ultimate truth-, rooting in the Nagarjuna's philosophy of the Middle Way or Mahayana school of Buddhism, we see the great difference between conventional justice and ultimate justice, and yet despite this difference they are critically the same. An understanding of this paradox is a journey of remarkable insight and clarity. Nagarjuna's doctrine of the emptiness of emptiness is imperative on this account.²⁰⁸

We've forwarded the idea on the conventional existence of Civil Justice²⁰⁹, where justice is affirmed in all its complexity, with its levels and facets in every case/trial. In our opinion the conventional existence of Civil Justice doesn't depend only upon Law and Judicial Reforms but upon the consciousness.

We've hypothesized that:

- civil justice depends upon the judicial discretion/legal creativity,

201 Carlo Rovelli: All Reality Is Interaction. See: <https://onbeing.org/programs/carlo-rovelli-all-reality-is-interaction/>

202 The term interaction is field-defining, yet surprisingly confused. This essay discusses what interaction is: Hornbæk Kasper, Oulasvirta Antti, What Is Interaction? (2017): https://www.researchgate.net/publication/313859745_What_Is_Interaction

203 The article does not discuss the Aristotle's taxonomy of justice in the Nicomachean Ethics, three kinds of justice - distributive justice, rectificatory or corrective or commutative justice, and reciprocal justice - and the difference between natural justice and conventional justice and uses the term "Conventional" in the sense of Nagarjuna and Carlo Rovelli.

204 Olga Papkova. CIVIL JUSTICE DISCRETION CONSCIOUSNESS MINDFULNESS. Authorea. February 18, 2021. DOI: 10.22541/au.161360710.05001740/v1

205 A philosophical concept created by Henri Laborit and introduced by Edgar Morin. Edgar Morin (8 July 1921) is a French philosopher and sociologist who has been internationally recognized for his work on complexity and "complex thought" (*pensée complexe*) and for his scholarly contributions to such diverse fields as media studies, politics, sociology, visual anthropology, ecology, education, and systems biology. He holds degrees in history, economics, and law.

206 Our paper has presented a rigorous empirical exploration of the ideas of George Herbert Mead: Gillespie Alex, *Becoming Other: From Social Interaction to Self-Reflection*, Information Age Pub Inc, (2006).

207 <https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/twotruths-tibet/>

208 During our work we use the brilliant works of Jay Garfield. Jay Lazar Garfield (1955) is an American professor of philosophy who specializes in Tibetan Buddhism. He also specializes on the philosophy of mind, cognitive science, epistemology, metaphysics, philosophy of language, ethics, and hermeneutics. He is currently Doris Silbert Professor in the Humanities at Smith College, Professor of Philosophy at the University of Melbourne, Visiting Professor of Philosophy and Buddhist Studies at Harvard Divinity School, and Adjunct Professor of Philosophy at the Central University of Tibetan Studies

209 The paper does not discuss the Aristotle's taxonomy of justice in the Nicomachean Ethics, three kinds of justice - distributive justice, rectificatory or corrective or commutative justice, and reciprocal justice - and the difference between natural justice and conventional justice and uses the term "Conventional" in the sense of Nagarjuna and Carlo Rovelli. Using it in that way it does not distinguish between the naturally just and the conventionally just. Instead of the idea that Justice represents some kind of juridical standard (see for ex: <http://the-stewardship.org/standard.htm>), the author insists that it concerns *inter alia* the intrinsic ethical\spiritual mindful demand on judges.

- the judicial discretion/legal creativity is based on legal consciousness,
- legal consciousness is the necessary part of the road to conventional/ultimate justice,
- legal consciousness makes the part of consciousness – as well as of awareness and mindfulness - the consciousness, the awareness and the mindfulness are the conditional parts of the road to conventional/ultimate justice.²¹⁰

In the paper titled “Finding Ways to Be Lawyers in Today's World, etc”²¹¹ we’ve tried to prove that Justice has energy-matter duality.

Wave–particle duality is the concept in quantum mechanics that every particle or quantum entity may be described as either a particle or a wave. It expresses the inability of the classical concepts "particle" or "wave" to fully describe the behavior of quantum-scale objects. As Albert Einstein wrote: "It seems as though we must use sometimes the one theory and sometimes the other, while at times we may use either. We are faced with a new kind of difficulty. We have two contradictory pictures of reality; separately neither of them fully explains the phenomena of light, but together they do."²¹²

Now, in our furtive little mind we immediately see the implications of this particle/wave anomaly. When a photon is in a wave form it is spirit (Justice) and when it is in a particle form it is matter (Justice). This explains in a limited way how spirit is non-local and omnipresent. But in order to appear to man Justice-spirit has to become a particle (judge/lawyer) and enter into the world of Justice-matter.

In the paper titled “Civil Justice, Discretion, Consciousness, Mindfulness etc”²¹³ we’ve tried to show that Spirituality (Consciousness) develops when we dedicate our freedom to something greater and more important than ourselves, with which we identify. A judge develops spirituality (consciousness) when he/she dedicates his/her freedom to justice, with which he/she identifies.

In order to achieve justice, a judge should go out of himself.

The spiritual (mindful) judge lives the experience of himself with all his aspects integrated. The spiritual (mindful) judge works on his own interiority, but uses his body, he/she is aware that as a body he/she depends on nature, as a judge he/she depends on the judiciary, law, the rule of law, he/she knows that there is a human dimension of justice that cannot be reduced to the bios, nor to the judiciary, it is free, where the judge can act with discretion, he can create justice that was not there before; he knows that freedom is precious and therefore must be cared for, supervised, disciplined, and that the justice happens if the judge relates to a larger dimension, to superior intelligence, to top values, to Justice-Spirit. Justice-spirit is not local. It’s onnipresent. Justice spirit is a Higher Consciousness²¹⁴.

There are the different meanings of the term “higher consciousness” and similar phrases in regard to personal development. Let’s take some of them we find more appropriate here. We share the Faggin’s concept of consciousness units (CUs), the fundamental “components” of all that exists: space, time and the quantum fields of the fundamental particles.²¹⁵ He forwards the idea that “a quantum field is a conscious self, a part-whole,

210 Olga Papkova. CIVIL JUSTICE DISCRETION CONSCIOUSNESS MINDFULNESS. Authorea. February 18, 2021. DOI:10.22541/au.161360710.05001740/v1

211 Olga Nickole Kuyan. (2021). Finding Ways to Be Lawyers in Today's World, Calling to Have the Courage to Make Changes. Mindfulness Matters: Thought, Attention, Awakening. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5734445>

212 Einstein Albert, Infeld Leopold. The Evolution of Physics: The Growth of Ideas from Early Concepts to Relativity and Quanta, Cambridge University Press (1938) <https://ui.adsabs.harvard.edu/abs/1938epgi.book...E/abstract>

213 Olga Papkova. CIVIL JUSTICE DISCRETION CONSCIOUSNESS MINDFULNESS. Authorea. February 18, 2021. DOI: 10.22541/au.161360710.05001740/v1

214 Bunge Marcia JoAnn, ed, The Child in Christian Thought, Wm. B. Eerdmans Publishing, 341 (2001). While the concept has ancient roots, dating back to the Bhagavad Gita and Indian Vedas, it was significantly developed in German idealism, and is a central notion in contemporary popular spirituality.

215 <http://www.fagginfoundation.org/articles/the-fundamental-nature-of-reality/>

while the quantum fields described by physics represent only the outer symbolic aspects of the selves."²¹⁶

"To higher order consciousness, the ability to be conscious of being conscious, to tell a narrative..."²¹⁷ - Gerald Maurice Edelman²¹⁸ says.

Modern scientists argue that the contents of consciousness are a subset of the experiences, emotions, thoughts and beliefs that are generated by non-conscious processes within our brains. This subset takes the form of a personal narrative, which is constantly being updated. The personal narrative exists in parallel with our personal awareness, but the latter has no influence over the former. They argue that it is the ability to communicate the contents of one's personal narrative — and not personal awareness — that gives humans their unique evolutionary advantage.²¹⁹

Earlier, applying the Stream of consciousness,²²⁰ which has become famous especially through the novels of James Joyce²²¹, we've found that every personal narrative (of a judge/lawyer and of other trial's participants) communicates and every justice vibrates with the others as justice is part of the world. Thanks to this, a judge is given to internalize, to broaden every case, to identify it with the whole justice,²²² following Russian Philosopher Pavel Nikolaevič Evdokimov's²²³ thought: "every part of the world vibrates empathically with the others. Thanks to this immanence, man is given to internalize, to expand his place, to identify it, from an ethical point of view, with the whole world".²²⁴

Inter alia, let us attract your attention to a systematic framework, derived from the Vedic tradition of India by Maharishi Mahesh Yogi²²⁵, for the development of higher states of consciousness. Maharishi's teaching on consciousness can be seen in his 1994 book Maharishi Vedic University – Introduction²²⁶, to unfold at three levels: individual, collective

216 <http://www.fagginfoundation.org/articles/the-nature-of-consciousness/>

217 <https://www.abc.net.au/radionational/programs/allinthemind/nobel-laureate-gerald-edelman-on-consciousness/2989818#:~:text=Gerald%20Edelman%3A%20To%20higher%20order.or%20make%20up%20a%20deceit.>

218 Gerald Maurice Edelman (1929 – 2014) was an American biologist who shared the 1972 Nobel Prize in Physiology or Medicine for work with Rodney Robert Porter on the immune system. There is a continuity between his work on the immune system, for which he won the Nobel Prize, and his later work in neuroscience and in philosophy of mind.

219 See Oakley David A, Halligan Peter here:

<https://theconversation.com/what-if-consciousness-is-not-what-drives-the-human-mind-86785>

220 It was the French psychologist and philosopher Victor Egger (1848-1909), in the essay *La parole intérieure. Essai de psychologie descriptive* (1881), the first to speak of "stream of consciousness", a theme that developed even more under the influence of Sigmund Freud with his texts on psychoanalysis and the unconscious.

221 James Augustine Aloysius Joyce (1882 – 1941) was an Irish novelist and poet, considered to be one of the most influential writers in the modernist avant-garde of the early 20th century. Joyce is best known for *Ulysses* (1922), a landmark work in which the episodes of Homer's *Odyssey* are paralleled in an array of contrasting literary styles, perhaps most prominent among these the stream of consciousness technique he perfected. Other major works are the short-story collection *Dubliners* (1914), and the novels *A Portrait of the Artist as a Young Man* (1916) and *Finnegans Wake* (1939). His complete oeuvre also includes three books of poetry, a play, occasional journalism, and his published letters.

222 Olga Papkova. CIVIL JUSTICE DISCRETION CONSCIOUSNESS MINDFULNESS. Authorea. February 18, 2021. DOI: 10.22541/au.161360710.05001740/v1

223 Paul Evdokimov, originally Russian Павел Николаевич Евдокимов (1901-1970) was an Orthodox theologian. He was professor of theology at the Institut de Théologie Orthodoxe Saint-Serge in Paris.

224 See in: Dostoevskij e il problema del male, Città Nuova, Roma, 152 (1995).

225 Maharishi Mahesh Yogi (1918 – 2008) was an Indian yoga guru. After earning a degree in physics at Allahabad University in 1942, Maharishi Mahesh Yogi became an assistant and disciple of Swami Brahmananda Saraswati (also known as Guru Dev), the Shankaracharya (spiritual leader) of the Jyotir Math in the Indian Himalayas. The Maharishi credits Brahmananda Saraswati with inspiring his teachings. In 1955, the Maharishi began to introduce his Transcendental Deep Meditation (later renamed Transcendental Meditation) to India and the world.

The Maharishi is reported to have trained more than 40,000 TM teachers, taught the Transcendental Meditation technique to "more than five million people" and founded thousands of teaching centres and hundreds of colleges, universities and schools.

226 Maharishi Mahesh Yogi (1994) *Maharishi Vedic University – Introduction*. Holland, Maharishi Vedic University Press, ISBN 90-7175-017-5

and fundamental. With reference to waking, dreaming and sleeping, he defines a fourth state: "Those who practice Transcendental Meditation have the experience that Transcendental Consciousness is unbounded awareness – it is pure wakefulness; it is fully awake within itself; it knows only itself and nothing else. This experience of self-referral unbounded awareness enlivens the holistic level of functioning of the whole brain physiology."²²⁷

We see a series of stable stages beyond currently conceived endpoints of development are described, based upon the unfoldment of "pure" consciousness as a stable underlying basis of experience. Pure consciousness is consciousness aware of itself as an unbounded field independent of all mental activity such as thought and feeling. The first of the higher stages is "cosmic consciousness,"²²⁸ in which pure consciousness is permanently maintained throughout all other experiences. A substantive body of research supports the uniqueness of the state of pure consciousness²²⁹ and the pattern of development predicted to occur with growth of cosmic consciousness.²³⁰

Teilhard de Chardin writes on Super-consciousness, that is the consciousness higher than ordinary men have, it could be developed within future mankind: "Mankind, forced to develop in a confined area, has now found itself subjected to an intense pressure. This pressure—combined with the nature of our thinking souls to coalesce—causes the radial energies of consciousness to concentrate toward a sort of super-consciousness. The final unification of our planet is the natural culmination of a cosmic process of organization which has never deviated since those remote ages when our Earth was young. Mankind has cosmic roots."²³¹

Development is predicted to further progress through the higher stages of "refined cosmic consciousness" to "unity consciousness," in which the individual is said to directly and permanently experience the underlying unity of the perceiver and the perceived, the subject (self) and object, as the field of pure consciousness.

Maharishi says: "Fruit of all knowledge' [means] the ability to live mistake-free life in higher states of consciousness, daily life in full accordance with all the Laws of Nature, with the spontaneous ability to do everything right and achieve anything."²³²

Moreover, the practice of a few individuals can have a direct effect on the environment: "Coherence in collective consciousness and positivity and harmony in national consciousness is produced by the group practice of Maharishi's Transcendental Meditation."²³³ Teilhard de Chardin confirms: "While in the individual brain thought emerges from a system of non-thinking nerve fibers, in the case of the collective brain, on the other hand, each element is, in turn, an autonomous center of reflection".²³⁴

It is necessary to imagine an evolution that responds to the needs of the quantities that exist in the Universe. Then the idea of super union becomes something plausible, not an illogical and senseless thing. If the Universe is immense, the evolutionary process can create something immense. To these considerations Chardin adds the fact that consciousness has always existed in the elements that evolve - he speaks of the inside of things - and has always expanded by becoming more and more mature up to our consciousness that is very complex. If this happened in the past, and the evolutionary

227 Maharishi Mahesh Yogi (1994) , Opt. Cit, 155, 260.

228 Cosmic Consciousness: A Study in the Evolution of the Human Mind is a 1901 book by the psychiatrist Richard Maurice Bucke, in which the author explores the concept of cosmic consciousness, which he defines as "a higher form of consciousness than that possessed by the ordinary man"

229 <https://neurosciencenews.com/pure-consciousness-18969/#:~:text=In%20the%20context%20of%20meditation,which%20they%20perceive%20consciousness%20itself.&text=We%20are%20interested%20in%20human,simplest%20form%20of%20conscious%20experience.>

230 <https://worldbusiness.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/01/Cosmic-Consciousness.pdf>

231 <https://www.organism.earth/library/document/survival-4>

232 Ibid.

233 Maharishi Mahesh Yogi (1994) , Opt. Cit, 280-281.

234 Chardin Pierre Teilhard, The Future of Man, 256 (1969)

motion has not stopped, it can be deduced that the development of consciousness continues to expand, also.

It's important to reflect on these ideas.

Consciousness is not only an experience lived consciously, but it is a process, a constantly evolving flow that has a social dimension, also.

The different perspectives extend current conceptions of development by locating a unified foundation of cognitive and affective processes, higher consciousness, as the basis of higher stages of development.

Diaphany Consciousness. We consider that the higher consciousness is Christ consciousness²³⁵, a Diaphany²³⁶ consciousness.

Christ Consciousness is an awareness of the higher self as part of a universal system.

Although it can be interpreted in a number of ways, a common understanding is that Christ Consciousness is the state of consciousness in which a person has found self-realization and unity with God or the Divine. It may also be used as a synonym for the yogic and Hindu concept of samadhi²³⁷, or deep spiritual bliss.²³⁸

It was named after the spiritual elevation Jesus achieved during his mortal life, and is symbolic of the enlightenment attained by spiritual masters after a period of suffering. This is a common concept among many different religious traditions and is not unique to Christianity. As such, Christ Consciousness is available to all those who seek awareness and spiritual awakening, regardless of their personal religious adherence.

We use the word Diaphany to evoke the process by which the nature of the whole Justice (Fairness) shines through its parts; how, like the facets of a diamond, phenomenal surfaces are revealed as unique, living expressions of the deeper, holarchical reality from which they draw their life.

Our idea roots in Chardin's thought. Besides his scientific work in geology and paleontology, especially related to the fossil origins of man in China, Chardin developed a philosophical and theological thought taking into account the evolutionary view of the world provided by science. His thought sprung from a deep spirituality and mystic experience.

Teilhard is aware that science is the main force that drives today human progress. The relation between matter and spirit, the convergence of the cosmic evolving process to what he has called the Omega Point, that is identified with the Christ. According to Teilhard, we can neither think of the universe without its center in Christ nor of Christ without being the center of the universe. This leads to the concepts of Cosmic or Universal Christ and the process of cosmogenesis becoming a Christogenesis. Thus the world becomes transparent to the present of Christ in what he calls the "Divine Milieu" and the "Christique".

Diaphany is one of the most beautiful neologisms that we find in Teilhard's writings. It is from the Greek: διαφάνεια - diafania: a word that in Greek has a much richer meaning than what we find in "diaphanous"²³⁹, which with its meaning of "partially transparent", it impoverishes its content. διαφάνεια indicates a reality that is totally "transparent", but is also "fiery" and "evident".

Teilhard gives all these meanings to the word "diafania (diaphanie)" to indicate that, through the Incarnation, God has not only manifested himself to the world (this is the etymological meaning of the word "epiphany"), but lives there and becomes transparent.

235 Although Christ Consciousness is not intended to relate solely to the personality of Jesus Christ, its combination of Christian language with Eastern religious and philosophical concepts make it a controversial term to some.

236 Diaphany / A diaphanous epiphany (Epiphany = A manifestation of some divine or super human being; Any sudden and important manifestation or realization, Diaphanous = Transparent; translucent; so light and insubstantial as to be almost transparent.)

237 <https://www.britannica.com/topic/samadhi-Indian-philosophy>

238 <https://www.spiritualawakeningprocess.com/2012/07/bliss-state-comes-and-then-it-goes.html>

239 Transparent or translucent; allowing light to pass through; capable of being seen through.

Based on the Chardin's beautiful idea, using the "Diaphania Consciousness", we intend Justice-Higher Consciousness, becoming transparent Justice-reality (conventional and ultimate).

With Diaphania Consciousness we refer to lawyers with vertical lives with gazes of mystic, capable of grasping the Justice as the true "Universe Environment" in which and through which Christ manifests himself and from this discovery Justice is born.

It is in the "Milieu Divin"²⁴⁰, written during the first years of his stay in China, that Teilhard focuses on that important concept, which is already present 'in a nutshell' since his first essays collected under the name of "Écrits du temps de la Guerre"²⁴¹.

Teilhard writes in the "Milieu Divin": "If I am allowed to slightly modify a sacred word, we will say that the great mystery of Christianity is not specifically the Appearance but the Transparency of God in the Universe. Oh! Yes, Lord, not only the ray that emerges, but the ray that penetrates. Not your Epiphany, Jesus, but your Diaphania"²⁴².

The Universe lets God shining through, and the word "Diaphania" expresses this ardent and almost tangible reality, better - says Teilhard - than the word "Epiphany", which indicates the manifestation of God in history through Jesus the Christ. Living beings, - Teilhard tells us again, - are not only spectators of this "diaphania", but are an integral part of it.²⁴³

On the basis of his unfolding the concept of consciousness, Maharishi declares: "The truth is that the Light of God is eternally the same, and it is available to the enlightened in his own self-referral consciousness, which is transcendental reality and is actually never influenced by the language in which it is expressed. In the language of religion, act in accordance with the Will of God; or, in the language of science, live life according to Natural Law."²⁴⁴ "Therefore the Light of God is the goal of every religion".²⁴⁵

The light is the goal of justice – we think. John Rawls said: "Justice is happiness according to virtue"²⁴⁶ In the paper titled "Social Values in Europe etc"²⁴⁷ we've sought to advance the idea that sophia energy-light energy-is within Justice. "Living well and beautifully and justly are all one thing,"²⁴⁸ — Socrates said. "Justice shines in very smoky homes, and honors the righteous; but the gold-spangled mansions where the hands are unclean she leaves with eyes averted"²⁴⁹, - Aeschylus tells us.

Following these thoughts we suppose that Justice shines by its own light and the "Diaphania Consciousness" expresses this reality better than the words "Critical Consciousness", "Justice Consciousness". Lawyers/judges are not only observers of the "diaphania", but are integral parts of it.

There is a beautiful letter from Teilhard, written just at the moment when he was reflecting on the concept of "diaphanous" and addressed, as wishes for the new year, to one of his most cultured and stimulating correspondents, the philosopher Leontine Zanta, that tells us: "Dear friend, may we be granted the corroborating vision of the mysterious Diaphania (I

240 <https://www.beweb.chiesacattolica.it/books/book/116832757/Le+Milieu+Divin+%3A+essai+de+vie+int%C3%A9rieure+-+Pierre+Teilhard+de+Chardin>

241 <https://www.edition-originale.com/it/letteratura/prime-edizione-e-preziosi-libri/teilhard-de-chardin-ecrits-du-temps-de-la-guerre-1916-1919-1965-32325>

242 Quoted in <https://www.teilhard.it/diaphania-0>

243 <http://eliasicons.blogspot.com/2011/09/teilhards-litany-13-monstrance.html>

244 Maharishi Mahesh Yogi (1994) Maharishi Vedic University – Introduction. Holland, Maharishi Vedic University Press, 230, 216 ISBN [90-7175-017-5](https://www.amazon.com/dp/90-7175-017-5)

245 Ibid.

246 <https://quotefancy.com/quote/1378710/John-Rawls-Justice-is-happiness-according-to-virtue>

247 Olga Nickole Papkova Kuyan. Social Values in Europe. Protecting Freedom of Thought, Conscience, Religion, Creating What?: Justice, Sophia, Phronesis. Authorea. July 14, 2021.

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248 <https://quotefancy.com/quote/908424/Socrates-Living-well-and-beautifully-and-justly-are-all-one-thing>

249 <https://quotefancy.com/quote/1062634/Aeschylus-Justice-shines-in-very-smoky-homes-and-honors-the-righteous-but-the-gold>

prefer this word to Epiphany ...) with which the universal Christ illuminates the unique and superior background of things, to act on us through them and to attract us to their common top!"²⁵⁰.

This does not do away with the Justice principles. In fact, the Justice can only be fulfilled in lawyers who walk according to the Justice-spirit, Higher Consciousness, Diaphania Consciousness, and not according to the matter.

When the rift is healed, the lawyers can live by the Higher Consciousness, Justice-spirit, from the inside out, rather than the Justice that works from the outside in.

It is really important for us to understand the dynamics of Justice way. The Justice can't be Justice (Fairness) without the Justice-Spirit (Diaphania Consciousness) and lawyers/judges who live vertical lives. Formal Applying of Justice Principles cannot guarantee justice achievement. Every lawyer/judge should enter into Diaphania Consciousness, in order for the rift to be healed in Justice. Then he/she should learn how to live in the power of that spirit/matter reconciliation. Quantum physics truly does help us to understand the dynamics of Justice way.

We share the Sandel's thought that "to achieve a just society we have to reason together about the meaning of the good life, and to create a public culture hospitable to the disagreements that will inevitably arise."²⁵¹

250 Quoted in <https://www.teilhard.it/diafania-0>

251 Michael J. Sandel, Justice: What's the Right Thing to Do?
https://www.goodreads.com/author/quotes/90763.Michael_J_Sandel